

Table S1. Sample Metadata

Name	Type	Species	Depth (m)	Location	Coordinates	Country	Sampling Year	Sequencing Year	Sequencing technology
Aply16	Sponge Tissue	Aplysina aerophoba	10,25	Cala Montgo	N42°06'52.20", E3°10'06.52"	Spain	2014	2014	Hybrid Illumina Pacbio
Aply21	Sponge Tissue	Aplysina aerophoba	10,25	Cala Montgo	N42°06'52.20", E3°10'06.52"	Spain	2014	2014	Hybrid Illumina Pacbio
Aply22	Sponge Tissue	Aplysina aerophoba	10,25	Cala Montgo	N42°06'52.20", E3°10'06.52"	Spain	2014	2014	Hybrid Illumina Pacbio
Aply23	Sponge Tissue	Aplysina aerophoba	10,25	Cala Montgo	N42°06'52.20", E3°10'06.52"	Spain	2014	2014	Hybrid Illumina Pacbio
Pf4	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Semi-dark zone)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina
Pf5	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Semi-dark zone)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina
Pf6	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Semi-dark zone)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina
Pf7	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Dark zone)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina
Pf8	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Dark zone)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina
Pf9	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Dark zone)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina
Pf10	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Entrance)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina
Pf11	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Entrance)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina
Pf12	Sponge Tissue	Petrocia ficiformis	5,5	Sfakia, Crete (Entrance)	N35°12'0.7", E24°7'09.8"	Greece	2018	2018	Illumina

ga3	Sponge Tissue	Geodia atlantica	150	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb1	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	450	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb2_2	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	150	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb4_2	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	150	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb5_2	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	150	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb6	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	150	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb7	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	450	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb8_2	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	450	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb9	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	450	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb10	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	450	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb126	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	1213	Davis Strait	N62°52'15.1", W58°37'34.32"	Canada	2015	2018	Illumina
gb278	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	1335	Davis Strait	N61°53'36.13", W60°7'57.612"	Canada	2014	2018	Illumina
gb305	Sponge Tissue	Geodia barretti	1437	Davis Strait	N62°31'6.24", W59°58'13.872"	Canada	2014	2018	Illumina
gb1_f	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	150	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb2_f	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	150	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina

gb3_f	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	150	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb5_6_f	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	450	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb9_f	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	450	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
gb10_f	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	450	Scengsbukt-Korsfjord	N60°8'8", E5°6'42"	Norway	2017	2018	Illumina
sw_7	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	10,25	Cala Montgo	N42°06'52.20", E3°10'06.52"	Spain	2014	2014	Illumina
sw_8	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	10,25	Cala Montgo	N42°06'52.20", E3°10'06.52"	Spain	2014	2014	Illumina
sw_9	Filtered Sea Water	N.a.	10,25	Cala Montgo	N42°06'52.20", E3°10'06.52"	Spain	2014	2014	Illumina
DOM10	Sponge Tissue	Smenospongia sp.	101	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2020	Illumina Novaseq6000 and Oxford Nanopore MinION
DOM14B	Sponge Tissue	Caminius sp.	230	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2020	Illumina Novaseq6000 and Oxford Nanopore MinION
DOM33	Sponge Tissue	Aplysina sp.	106	Cottage	N15°36'54.66", W61°27'48.93"	Dominica	2016	2020	Illumina Novaseq6000 and Oxford Nanopore MinION
DOM43	Sponge Tissue	Aciculites cribrophora	213	Connor Bay	N15°38'14.13", W61°27'39.13"	Dominica	2017	2020	Illumina Novaseq6000 and Oxford Nanopore MinION
DOM40	Sponge Tissue	Petrosia hartmani	146,304	Connor bay	N15°38'14.13", W61°27'39.13"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6000 and Oxford Nanopore MinION
DOM005	Sponge Tissue	Siphonodictyon coralliphagum	137	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6000

DOM007A	Sponge Tissue	Oceanapia bartschi	82	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6001
DOM007B	Sponge Tissue	Oceanapia bartschi	82	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6002
DOM011	Sponge Tissue	Neopetrosia spp.	134	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6003
DOM012A	Sponge Tissue	Aplysina sp.	134	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6004
DOM013	Sponge Tissue	Svenzea zeai	223	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6005
DOM015	Sponge Tissue	Svenzea zeai	107	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6006
DOM016	Sponge Tissue	Oceanapia bartschi	108	Portsmouth	N15°34'33.24", W61°27'20.16"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6007
DOM026	Sponge Tissue	Verongula sp	144,78	Cottage	N15°36'54.66", W61°27'48.93"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6008
DOM044	Sponge Tissue	Neopetrosia spp.	144	Connor bay	N15°38'14.13", W61°27'39.13"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6009
DOM045	Sponge Tissue	Verongula sp	149,352	Connor bay	N15°38'14.13", W61°27'39.13"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6010
DOM049	Sponge Tissue	Xestospongia sp.	140	Connor bay	N15°38'14.13", W61°27'39.13"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6011
DOM057	Sponge Tissue	Oceanapia bartschi	113	Connor bay	N15°38'14.13", W61°27'39.13"	Dominica	2016	2022	Illumina Novaseq6012

Table S2. Nucleotide sequence of the additional characterized FDHs used to supplement Fisher et al.'s dataset.

>MARME_bmp2

MNTNANYDVVIIGSGPAGSLCGIECRKKGLSVLCIEKDEFPRFHIGESLTGNAGQIITDLGLYDKMEEAEFPNKLGVNVIGLSKNEFFIPILAKTWQVRRSSFDKMLKEKALEHGVEYQTGMVTDVLRDGEKVVGATYKTAAGSQNVN SKVLVDASGQTTFLSRKGVAGKRKVEFFSQQIASFAHFENVERDLPPFSTNTTILYSKQYHWSWIIPISPTDLSLGVIPKDLYYKECNSPEAAIEWGMNNISPCLKRRFKNAEQVEASQSMADFSYRIEPFVGDGWLCIGDASHRFLDPIFS YGVVSGMKEGIRSAEAIATSIGTDWKTTPFYAFRDWSNKGQQAADLIRYFWIYPIFFGYQMNPDLRDEVIRLL GGCCFDCEGWKAPSIFSNAIKEYDRKQMETKIAS*

>MARME_bmp5

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>bmp5_PLPH

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>PL2TA16_bmp5

MNKTIAVIGAGLSGIAAVKQLTDGGHQVTCFEKAESFGGVFADKKIYDDLHLTISNYFMAYS DYVPNHQKLFWS SKKEYINYLGEYIERFDIAKHIHYDHEVCCVQKQGDWLVTYKNADTEQTKFDMVAVCSGHFQKPKLPDLPGL DMYQGNIEHSNDYRDKHN YAGKRVLCVGLGESSADITSEISQVARKCILSLRRYPVAVAPRYMAFQEDPYFTIDTS WLTSRIVNKLPHRYHGGITKGIFNKYVTSRNDHVRIRGEWLKKS GSPSHHQAVTKNERLFRPIADGKVPVNI GGIE RFEKNAVVFQDGTREEIDAVVFCTGYQLSFPFLDVSISNMRDLYKQMFIPEMGHLSFIGFVRPQQGGIPVIAEM QCRYLSKLASGEAQLPTLSEMHDVIKYDTKHQWTEYKITPHVASLVNYCHYMDSVAKLVGCMQPISLFDKDPML RVKLLHNPQFAAQYRLDGPNNMTHHTAREFLLSFPNISSWPRIIHFEVALAAQKLLSRLRLDGLREISK*

>PL2TA16_bmp2

MSEFKSYDVVIIGSGPAGSLCGIECRKKGLSVLCIEKDEFPRFHIGESLTGNAGQIIRDGLAEEMDAAGFPDKPGV NVIGLSKNEFFIPILAPTQVQRSDFDNMLKRKALEHGVEYQQGLVKDVIKHDGKVVGAIYKADDMEHQVRS KVLVDASGQNTFLSRKGIAGKREIEFFSQQIASFAHYKGVVERDLPPFSTNTTILYSKQYHWSWIIPISPTDLSLGI VPKDLYYKECKNPDDAIEWGMENISPEIRRRFQNAERIGDSQSMADFSYRIEPFVGDGWLCIGDAHRFLDPIFSYG VSFAMKEGIRAAAIKQAIDGNDWKTTPFYAYRDWSNKGQQAADLIRYFWIYPIFFGYQMNPDLRDEVIRLL GGCCFDCEGWKAPTIFRNAIEEYDRKQMVG*

>PLSP_bmp2

MNGFTHYDVVIIGSGPAGSLCGIECRKKGLSVLCIEKEQFPRFHIGESLTGNAGQIIRDLGLAEEMDAAGFPDKP GVNIGLSKNEFFIPILAPTQVQRSDFDNMLKRKAVEHGVEYKLGMMVTDVIKDGKVVGALYKADGVEHQV RSKVLVDASGQNTFLSRKGVAGKRQIEFFSQQIASFAHYKGVVERDLPPFSTNTTILYSKQYHWSWIIPISPTDSL GVVIPKDLYYKECKNPDDAIAWGMHDHISPELKRFRKNAERQGDSQSMADFSYRIEPFVGDGWMCIGDAHRFL DPIFSYGVSFAMKEGIRAAEIAQVAVAGQDWKAPFYAYRDWSNKGQQAADLIRYFWIYPIFFGYQMNPDLR DEVIRLLGGCCFDCEGWKAPAIFRNAIEEYDRKQMAS*

>PLPC_AltN

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GANFKQDDFQEFFDFSKNYTDGWTWTWQVPRDDFDNVLAEVQKMGAPIIEFGTSVVDANMDLEEPIIKVVN
EAGDVQEIQAKFVVDSSGYGRVLANLLDLNEPSSAPTRATLFAQFKPADGIETGAENNKVTLVHEEDVWWLI
PFSDGHVSVGFVGNPEYLESAEGDAKTRFLTYLARDQHASAMLDGLALCMPEPKEIKGYSKGIKQLFGKNFVLTG
NASEFIDPVFSAGVMFAIESGARAADLIVAQLNGEEADWQQDYEAHMLKGIAMRTYIEGWYDGRLLRRLFFSD
NKPEKIKSQITSVLAGYVWDETNPVNRSEKTLNLLSELHNNPEMA*

>GUM202_bmp5

MLDCIVIGAGSGGLVTTKELLEQGVGEVVCLEQAEDVGGVFTNTYDSLVLTSATISMFSDFWIGDGNQHKFW
TKDEVVDYWKYAEHFGVREHIRFGSKVVAVVEQGGEGWQVQLASGENLLTKRVALAIGNNAIPKYPEWKELL
TEVEYSHSQDYRNADRFAKTVLAVGGGESGADIALEISRVASKCWVSLRNSAGWIVPRRRGINAADISTHRGV
WGLPRDYGAVLTEAVNQAELSQKDPVYDTPVKLNQKVEAKKIWGFATKNFSLPKAIVNHGCKVVGEIVKVE
DGGRTLHTADGECLTNVDAVVFSTGYKNAVSFLPEELKQTDPRGLYKHMFPKYQDKLVWIGWARPNGFSQF
PIMEMQARLFALICKGELALPAPVEMEKVACIDRATYLEQFENNAHQVRSVDYHRYIDDMASLIGCEPPLWQY
FFLHPRIWLRMVYGAIQSTQFRLRGPNGKESLARELLMKLPVSKPTHIVKAGLKGRVIYAFKALIPKIIFVGLGSRK
SSSSLAVSRVSS*

>GUM202_bmp18

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TKDEAVDYWKRYAEHFGVLERIRFNSKVVAVVEQGGREGWQIQLESKDILLSKRLALATGNNAIPNYPEWKNLLT
HVEYFHSQEYRNADMFDKKNVLAVGGGESGADIALELSSVASQCWVSIRNTMGWVATRKRSLGKVVAAADV
ALNRLVWAMSGKTITKVIQADLIEQDPVFDAVELNKKIKGSNGIWFIFGTKNFSFPKAIVYHGCKVVGEIVKV
EDGGRTLHTAEGECLNVDAVVFSTGYKNAVSFLPEELKQTDPRSLYKHMFPKYRDKIVWIGWARPNGYGSQF
PVMEMQARLFALICKGELALPATAEMERVACIDRVANLEQFDHAYRVRSLVDYHHYMDDMASLIGCKPSLW
KYLFSAPRICLPLVFAAIQGTQFRLQGPNGKESLARKILIKLPIIVPTPIVKGLLRQSLADALSRLGR*

Table S3. GCF metadata. Features each GCF's samples, host sponge species, MAGs and MAG predicted taxonomy.

GCF	Samples	Host_taxa	dRep representative MAGs	MAG taxonomy
1896	Aply16,Aply22,DOM005,DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM012A,DOM015,DOM026,DOM044,Pf11	Oceanapia bartschi,Neopetrosia sp.,Aplysina aerophoba,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Verongula sp.,Siphonodictyon coralliphagum	-,Aply23_bin.19.fa,Aply16_bin.2.fa,DOM005_bin.9.fa,DOM012A_bin.2.fa,DOM016_bin.19.fa,DOM044_bin.14.fa,Pf11_bin.65.fa	-,p__Poribacteria;g__WGA-3G;s__p__Poribacteria;g__s__
1	Aply16,Aply22	Aplysina aerophoba	Aply22_bin.11.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__MSPOR6;s__
2002	Aply16,DOM013,DOM015,DOM044,DOM045,DOM10,DOM33,DOM40,DOM43,Pf12,Pf6,gb2_2,gb9	Neopetrosia sp.,Petrosia hartmani,Aplysina aerophoba,Aciculites cribrophora,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Verongula sp.,Geodia barretti NOR,Smenospongia sp.	Aply16_bin.4.fa,-,DOM045_bin.26.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__,-
2249	Aply16,Aply23,DOM14B,Pf10,Pf11,Pf6,Pf7,Pf8,Pf9	Caminus sp.,Aplysina aerophoba,Petrocia ficiformis	-,Pf4_bin.17.fa,DOM14B_bin.52.fa	-,p__Acidobacteriota;g__Bin61;s__
5	Aply16	Aplysina aerophoba	-	-
2364	Aply21,Aply23,DOM43,Pf11,Pf12,Pf5,Pf6,Pf7,Pf9	Aplysina aerophoba,Petrocia ficiformis,Aciculites cribrophora	Aply21_bin.12.fa,DOM43_bin.49.fa,-,Pf4_bin.24.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__,-
7	Aply21	Aplysina aerophoba	Pf12_bin.33.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__WGA-3G;s__WGA-3Gsp000406005
2043	Aply21,DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM013,DOM016,DOM057,DOM10,Pf12,Pf4,Pf9	Oceanapia bartschi,Aplysina aerophoba,Svenzea zeai,Petrocia ficiformis,Smenospongia sp.	-,DOM016_bin.19.fa,DOM10_bin.83.fa,Pf9_bin.14.fa,Pf9_bin.10.fa	-,p__Poribacteria;g__s__
2281	Aply21,Pf10,Pf11,Pf12,Pf4,Pf6,Pf8	Aplysina aerophoba,Petrocia ficiformis	Aply23_bin.19.fa,Pf9_bin.24.fa,-	p__Poribacteria;g__WGA-3G;s__,-
10	Aply21	Aplysina aerophoba	-	-
2361	Aply22,Pf9	Aplysina aerophoba,Petrocia ficiformis	Aply22_bin.45.fa,Pf9_bin.57.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__Bin95;s__
2040	Aply22,DOM057	Aplysina aerophoba,Oceanapia bartschi	Aply22_bin.44.fa,DOM007B_bin.12.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__

15	Aply22	Aplysina aerophoba	Pf4_bin.17.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__Bin61;s__
2559	Aply22,DOM012A,DOM10,DOM40,DOM43,Pf10,Pf11,Pf12,Pf4,Pf5,Pf7,gb10,gb1,gb278,gb2_2,gb305,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb6,gb7,gb8_2	Petrosia hartmani,Aplysina aerophoba,Aciculites cribrophora,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Geodia barretti CAN,Geodia barretti NOR,Smenospongia sp.,Geodia atlantica	- ,DOM10_bin.73.fa,Pf11_bin.39.fa,gb7_bin.52.fa,gb305_bin.22.fa	- ,p__Acidobacteriota;g__UBA8438;s__
2402	Aply22,DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM011,DOM016,DOM10,DOM33,Pf10,Pf11,Pf6,Pf7,gb126,gb305,gb3_2,gb5_2,gb7,gb8_2,gb9	Oceanapia bartschi,Neopetrosia sp.,Aplysina aerophoba,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Geodia barretti CAN,Geodia barretti NOR,Smenospongia sp.,Geodia atlantica	Pf7_bin.67.fa,DOM007A_bin.13.fa,DOM33_bin.49.fa,-,gb305_bin.13.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__s__,-
19	Aply23	Aplysina aerophoba	Aply23_bin.14.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__Bin36;s__Bin36 sp002239085
20	Aply23	Aplysina aerophoba	-	-
21	Aply23	Aplysina aerophoba	Aply21_bin.6.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
23	Aply23	Aplysina aerophoba	-	-
1912	DOM005,DOM013,DOM015,DOM026,DOM045,DOM10,DOM33,DOM40,Pf5	Petrosia hartmani,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.,Siphonodictyon coralliphagum	DOM005_bin.1.fa,DOM013_bin.35.fa,DOM40_bin.23.fa,DOM026_bin.32.fa,DOM10_bin.14.fa,Pf5_bin.13.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__PCPOR2b;s__
2027	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM016,DOM057	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM057_bin.59.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__PCPOR2b;s__
1823	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM016,DOM057,DOM40	Petrosia hartmani,Oceanapia bartschi	DOM057_bin.37.fa,DOM40_bin.4.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__GCA-2724215;s__
1853	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM013,DOM016,DOM057,DOM33,DOM40,gb4_2	Oceanapia bartschi,Petrosia hartmani,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Geodia barretti NOR	DOM007B_bin.31.fa,-	p__Poribacteria;g__s__,-

2039	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM011,DOM016,DOM044,DOM045,DOM057,DOM10,DOM14B,gb1,gb5_2,gb6	Oceanapia bartschi,Neopetrosia sp.,Caminus sp.,Verongula sp.,Geodia barretti NOR,Smenospongia sp.	- ,DOM057_bin.11.fa,DOM011_bin.51.fa,DOM044_bin.2.fa,DOM045_bin.56.fa,DOM14B_bin.10.fa	- ,p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
1854	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM013,DOM015,DOM016,DOM057	Svenzea zeai,Oceanapia bartschi	DOM015_bin.57.fa,-	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__,-
2506	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM33,Pf8,gb4_2,gb8_2	Aplysina sp.,Oceanapia bartschi,Petrocia ficiformis,Geodia barretti NOR	DOM007B_bin.3.fa,-	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__,-
1948	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM011,DOM015,DOM016,DOM026,DOM057,DOM10,DOM40	Oceanapia bartschi,Neopetrosia sp.,Petrosia hartmani,Svenzea zeai,Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.	DOM057_bin.24.fa,DOM40_bin.82.fa,DOM015_bin.24.fa,DOM10_bin.71.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__UBA8231;s__
1951	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM013,DOM015,DOM016,DOM057,DOM33,Pf4	Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Oceanapia bartschi,Petrocia ficiformis	DOM015_bin.57.fa,- ,DOM33_bin.26.fa,Pf10_bin.11.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__,-
2010	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM012A,DOM013,DOM015,DOM016,DOM026,DOM044,DOM045,DOM057,DOM40,DOM43	Oceanapia bartschi,Neopetrosia sp.,Petrosia hartmani,Aciculites cribrophora,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Verongula sp.	DOM016_bin.44.fa,DOM015_bin.62.fa,DOM011_bin.25.fa,DOM40_bin.61.fa,DOM43_bin.30.fa	p__Desulfobacterota_B;g__s__
1892	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM011,DOM012A,DOM026,DOM045,DOM057,DOM10,DOM14B,DOM33	Oceanapia bartschi,Neopetrosia sp.,Caminus sp.,Aplysina sp.,Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.	DOM007A_bin.28.fa,DOM011_bin.60.fa,DOM10_bin.80.fa,-	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__,-
1834	DOM007A,DOM007B	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM007A_bin.57.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2042	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM016,DOM026,DOM057,DOM10,DOM14B,DOM33	Oceanapia bartschi,Caminus sp.,Aplysina sp.,Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.	DOM007B_bin.45.fa,-	p__Poribacteria;g__s__,-

1983	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM016,DOM044,DOM057,DOM43	Oceanapia bartschi,Aciculites cribrophora,Neopetrosia sp.	DOM057_bin.52.fa,-,DOM43_bin.102.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__s__,-
1859	DOM007A,DOM007B	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM007B_bin.34.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__MSPOR6;s__
1838	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM016,DOM057	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM007A_bin.65.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__s__
1839	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM016,DOM057	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM007B_bin.47.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2033	DOM007A,DOM016,DOM057	Oceanapia bartschi	-,DOM057_bin.20.fa	-,p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
1959	DOM007A,DOM016,DOM057	Oceanapia bartschi	-	-
1843	DOM007A,DOM012A,DOM016,DOM057	Aplysina sp.,Oceanapia bartschi	DOM057_bin.66.fa,DOM012A_bin.13.fa	p__Actinobacteriota;g__s__
2044	DOM007A,DOM007B,DOM016,DOM049,DOM057,Pf5,Pf6,gb5_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR,Oceanapia bartschi,Petrocia ficiformis,Xestospongia muta	DOM057_bin.42.fa,-,DOM049_bin.6.fa,Pf11_bin.39.fa,gb7_bin.52.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__UBA8438;s__,-
1845	DOM007A	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM007A_bin.11.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
1846	DOM007A,DOM33	Aplysina sp.,Oceanapia bartschi	-,DOM33_bin.5.fa	-,p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
2045	DOM007A,DOM011,DOM016,DOM044,DOM057	Oceanapia bartschi,Neopetrosia sp.	DOM40_bin.36.fa,-	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__,-
1851	DOM007B,DOM057	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM007B_bin.47.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
1869	DOM007B	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM057_bin.66.fa	p__Actinobacteriota;g__s__
1870	DOM007B	Oceanapia bartschi	-	-

2009	DOM011,DOM012A,DOM045,DOM10,DOM33,DOM40	Neopetrosia sp.,Petrosia hartmani,Aplysina sp.,Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.	DOM011_bin.47.fa,DOM33_bin.36.fa,DOM33_bin.22.fa,DOM40_bin.51.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__s__
2410	DOM011,gb10,gb1,gb5_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR,Neopetrosia sp.	DOM011_bin.33.fa,gb6_bin.52.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__Bin61;s__
1876	DOM011	Neopetrosia sp.	-	-
2487	DOM011,gb10,gb1,gb2_2,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR,Neopetrosia sp.,Geodia atlantica	-	-
1879	DOM011,DOM013,DOM015,DOM026,DOM10,DOM40	Neopetrosia sp.,Petrosia hartmani,Svenzea zeai,Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.	DOM007A_bin.65.fa,DOM10_bin.10.fa,-	p__Latescibacterota;g__s__,-
1880	DOM011	Neopetrosia sp.	DOM011_bin.50.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
1881	DOM011	Neopetrosia sp.	DOM011_bin.50.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
1998	DOM011,DOM044,DOM10,DOM33	Aplysina sp.,Neopetrosia sp.,Smenospongia sp.	DOM33_bin.9.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__s__
1883	DOM011	Neopetrosia sp.	DOM011_bin.50.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
1884	DOM011,DOM012A,DOM026,DOM10,DOM33,DOM40,DOM43,Pf10,Pf4,Pf7	Neopetrosia sp.,Petrosia hartmani,Aciculites cribrophora,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.	DOM33_bin.28.fa,DOM10_bin.94.fa,DOM40_bin.33.fa,DOM43_bin.28.fa,Pf10_bin.11.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
1885	DOM011	Neopetrosia sp.	-	-
1886	DOM011,DOM14B,DOM33,gb7	Caminus sp.,Aplysina sp.,Neopetrosia sp.,Geodia barretti NOR	DOM044_bin.25.fa,DOM14B_bin.48.fa,-	p__Poribacteria;g__s__,-
2549	DOM011,DOM044,gb1,gb1_f,gb5_2,gb5_6_f,gb6	Geodia barretti NOR,Neopetrosia sp.,Seawater ATL	-	-
2322	DOM012A,DOM044,DOM10,DOM43,Pf7	Neopetrosia sp.,Aciculites cribrophora,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Smenospongia sp.	DOM012A_bin.14.fa,DOM044_bin.23.fa,-,DOM43_bin.21.fa,Pf7_bin.1.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__s__,-
2138	DOM012A,DOM013,DOM026,DOM045,DOM14B,DOM33,DOM40,DOM43	Petrosia hartmani,Aciculites cribrophora,Caminus sp.,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Verongula sp.	DOM40_bin.36.fa,-,DOM43_bin.77.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__,-

1895	DOM012A	Aplysina sp.	DOM012A_bin.42.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Defluviicoccus;s__
1897	DOM012A	Aplysina sp.	-	-
2508	DOM012A,DOM013,DOM015,DOM026,DOM10,DOM14B,DOM40,Pf10,Pf12,Pf8,gb10,gb126,gb2_2,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb8_2,gb9	Petrosia hartmani,Caminus sp.,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Geodia barretti CAN,Verongula sp.,Geodia barretti NOR,Smenospongia sp.,Geodia atlantica	- ,DOM013_bin.51.fa,DOM015_bin.46.fa, DOM14B_bin.24.fa	- ,p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__
1900	DOM012A,DOM33	Aplysina sp.	DOM012A_bin.42.fa,-	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Defluviicoccus;s__,-
1902	DOM012A	Aplysina sp.	-	-
1903	DOM012A,DOM016,DOM40	Petrosia hartmani,Aplysina sp.,Oceanapia bartschi	-,DOM016_bin.6.fa	- ,p__Poribacteria;g__ WGA-3G;s__
2098	DOM012A,DOM14B,DOM33	Caminus sp.,Aplysina sp.	-,DOM14B_bin.45.fa,DOM026_bin.47.fa	- ,p__Tectomicrobia;g__ SXND01;s__
1909	DOM013	Svenzea zeai	DOM015_bin.42.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2553	DOM013,DOM044,DOM049,DOM43,gb10,gb126,gb1,gb278,gb2_2,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb5_2,gb6,gb7,gb8_2,gb9	Neopetrosia sp.,Aciculites cribrophora,Svenzea zeai,Geodia barretti CAN,Geodia barretti NOR,Xestospongia muta,Geodia atlantica	DOM007A_bin.28.fa,- ,DOM049_bin.18.fa,gb8_2_bin.30.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__,-
1911	DOM013,DOM015,DOM026,DOM044,DOM057,DOM14B,DOM40,DOM43	Oceanapia bartschi,Neopetrosia sp.,Petrosia hartmani,Aciculites cribrophora,Caminus sp.,Svenzea zeai,Verongula sp.	DOM015_bin.30.fa,DOM33_bin.49.fa,DOM044_bin.6.fa,DOM007A_bin.13.fa,DOM14B_bin.41.fa,DOM40_bin.38.fa,DOM43_bin.81.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ ;s__
2036	DOM013,DOM015,DOM026,DOM045,DOM057,DOM10,DOM14B,DOM33,DOM43	Oceanapia bartschi,Aciculites cribrophora,Caminus sp.,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.,Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.	- ,DOM10_bin.9.fa,DOM057_bin.8.fa,DOM057_bin.57.fa,DOM14B_bin.25.fa	- ,p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__

1918	DOM013,DOM015,DOM049	Svenzea zeai,Xestospongia muta	DOM013_bin.24.fa,DOM049_bin.5.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__GCA-2724215;s__
1930	DOM013,DOM015	Svenzea zeai	-	-
1923	DOM015	Svenzea zeai	DOM015_bin.59.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__s__
2325	DOM015,DOM14B,DOM43,Pf7,gb10,gb2_2,gb6,gb7	Aciculites cribrophora,Caminus sp.,Svenzea zeai,Petrocia ficiformis,Geodia barretti NOR	DOM015_bin.49.fa,DOM14B_bin.29.fa,DOM43_bin.95.fa,Pf7_bin.59.fa,gb1_bin.4.fa,-	p__Latescibacterota;g__GCA-2724215;s__,-
1937	DOM015	Svenzea zeai	DOM015_bin.18.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2158	DOM015,DOM33,DOM40	Petrosia hartmani,Svenzea zeai,Aplysina sp.	DOM015_bin.19.fa	p__Deinococcota;g__MPNL01;s__MPNL01sp002239005
2453	DOM015,gb2_2,gb5_2	Svenzea zeai,Geodia barretti NOR	DOM007B_bin.31.fa,-,gb5_2_bin.1.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__s__,-
1941	DOM015	Svenzea zeai	-	-
2255	DOM026,DOM10,DOM14B,Pf10,Pf11,Pf12,Pf6,Pf7,Pf8	Verongula sp.,Smenospongia sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Caminus sp.	DOM026_bin.32.fa,DOM10_bin.47.fa,DOM10_bin.14.fa,-,Pf8_bin.6.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__PCPOR2b;s__,-
2123	DOM026,DOM33	Verongula sp.,Aplysina sp.	DOM33_bin.28.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
1975	DOM026	Verongula sp.	-	-
2286	DOM026,DOM044,DOM045,DOM33,DOM43,Pf12,Pf4,Pf5,Pf9	Neopetrosia sp.,Aciculites cribrophora,Aplysina sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Verongula sp.	,DOM044_bin.47.fa,DOM33_bin.71.fa,DOM43_bin.27.fa,Pf4_bin.17.fa,Pf5_bin.39.fa	- p__Acidobacteriota;g__Bin61;s__
1977	DOM026	Verongula sp.	-	-
1979	DOM026	Verongula sp.	-	-
1981	DOM026	Verongula sp.	DOM10_bin.73.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__UBA8438;s__
1985	DOM044	Neopetrosia sp.	DOM044_bin.33.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__

2077	DOM044,DOM10,DOM33	Aplysina sp.,Neopetrosia sp.,Smenospongia sp.	DOM044_bin.27.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__Bin90;s__
1987	DOM044	Neopetrosia sp.	DOM044_bin.13.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
1989	DOM044	Neopetrosia sp.	DOM044_bin.13.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
1992	DOM044	Neopetrosia sp.	DOM044_bin.42.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__Endozoicomonas;s__
1994	DOM044	Neopetrosia sp.	DOM044_bin.41.fa	p__Tectomicrobia;g__s__
1997	DOM044	Neopetrosia sp.	-	-
2554	DOM044,DOM40,gb10,gb2_2,gb4_2,gb6,gb8_2	Petrosia hartmani,Geodia barretti NOR,Neopetrosia sp.	DOM044_bin.25.fa,DOM40_bin.32.fa,-,gb4_2_bin.25.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__s__,-
2011	DOM045	Verongula sp.	DOM10_bin.30.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__GCA-2724215;s__
2012	DOM045	Verongula sp.	-	-
2013	DOM045,gb10,gb2_2,gb3_2,gb6,gb9	Verongula sp.,Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia atlantica	-,gb5_2_bin.1.fa	-,p__Poribacteria;g__s__
2014	DOM045	Verongula sp.	DOM045_bin.14.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__s__
2591	DOM045,DOM40,DOM43,gb10,gb3_f,gb4_2,gb8_2	Petrosia hartmani,Seawater ATL,Aciculites cribrophora,Verongula sp.,Geodia barretti NOR	-,DOM40_bin.52.fa	-,p__Chloroflexota;g__s__
2386	DOM045,DOM14B,gb10	Verongula sp.,Geodia barretti NOR,Caminus sp.	-	-
2017	DOM045	Verongula sp.	-	-
2359	DOM049,Pf10,Pf11,Pf5,Pf7,Pf9	Petrocia ficiformis,Xestospongia muta	DOM049_bin.10.fa,Pf10_bin.9.fa,Pf9_bin.40.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2019	DOM049	Xestospongia muta	DOM049_bin.10.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2020	DOM049	Xestospongia muta	DOM049_bin.14.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__Bin55;s__

2023	DOM049	Xestospongia muta	DOM049_bin.11.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__Bin61;s__
2025	DOM049	Xestospongia muta	-	-
2050	DOM057	Oceanapia bartschi	DOM057_bin.66.fa	p__Actinobacteriota;g__s__
2526	DOM057,DOM10,DOM14B,gb10,gb1,gb278,gb2_2,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb5_2,gb6,gb7,gb8_2,gb9	Oceanapia bartschi,Caminus sp.,Geodia barretti CAN,Geodia barretti NOR,Smenospongia sp.,Geodia atlantica	DOM057_bin.62.fa,DOM10_bin.95.fa,DOM14B_bin.70.fa,gb8_2_bin.1.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__Defluviicoccus;s__
2054	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	DOM10_bin.63.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__Bin61;s__
2056	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	DOM10_bin.95.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__Defluviicoccus;s__
2513	DOM10,gb4_2	Geodia barretti NOR,Smenospongia sp.	DOM10_bin.38.fa,gb5_2_bin.24.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__s__
2060	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	DOM10_bin.17.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__MSPOR6;s__
2061	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	DOM10_bin.94.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
2063	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	DOM10_bin.33.fa	p__Actinobacteriota;g__s__
2067	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	DOM011_bin.57.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2070	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	DOM011_bin.57.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2076	DOM10,Pf4,Pf8,gb278	Smenospongia sp.,Petrocia ficiformis,Geodia barretti CAN	DOM012A_bin.20.fa,-,DOM044_bin.16.fa,gb278_bin.45.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__,-
2080	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	-	-
2081	DOM10	Smenospongia sp.	DOM10_bin.59.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__s__
2084	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	-	-
2086	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	DOM14B_bin.5.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__

2557	DOM14B,gb1,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb6,gb8_2,gb9	Caminus sp.,Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia atlantica	DOM14B_bin.48.fa,gb4_2_bin.25.fa,-	p__Poribacteria;g__s__,-
2089	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	DOM14B_bin.17.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__UBA2168;s__
2090	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	DOM14B_bin.19.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
2091	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	DOM14B_bin.70.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__Defluviicoccus;s__
2092	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	-	-
2093	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	-	-
2333	DOM14B,Pf10,Pf11,Pf12,Pf4,Pf5,Pf6,Pf7,Pf8,Pf9	Caminus sp.,Petrocia ficiformis	DOM14B_bin.22.fa,Pf5_bin.31.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__MSPOR6;s__
2097	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	DOM14B_bin.76.fa	p__Verrucomicrobiota;g__s__
2271	DOM14B,Pf10,Pf4,Pf5,Pf6,Pf8	Caminus sp.,Petrocia ficiformis	-,Pf5_bin.19.fa	-,p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
2105	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	-	-
2108	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	DOM14B_bin.49.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2109	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	-	-
2110	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	-	-
2111	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	-	-
2112	DOM14B	Caminus sp.	-	-
2119	DOM33	Aplysina sp.	DOM33_bin.17.fa	p__Actinobacteriota;g__Bin76;s__
2127	DOM33	Aplysina sp.	DOM33_bin.72.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__MSPOR6;s__
2137	DOM33	Aplysina sp.	-	-
2139	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.21.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__s__
2141	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.45.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__s__

2143	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.64.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2144	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.50.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2147	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.50.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2153	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.77.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2154	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.70.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2161	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.64.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2163	DOM40	Petrosia hartmani	DOM40_bin.84.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ ;s__
2165	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.67.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2169	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.19.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2171	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.62.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ ;s__
2172	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.3.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__; s__
2173	DOM43,Pf11,Pf5	Petrocia ficiformis,Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.27.fa,Pf5_bin.39.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ _Bin61;s__
2174	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2175	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2176	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.93.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2177	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.47.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ _UBA8231;s__
2178	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.83.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ ;s__

2180	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.32.fa	p__Tectomicrobia;g__ ;s__
2183	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.12.fa	p__Verrucomicrobiota ;g__;s__
2184	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2185	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.54.fa	p__Actinobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2186	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.39.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ ;s__
2188	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2189	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.22.fa	p__;g__;s__
2190	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2191	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.62.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ ;s__
2192	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2193	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2194	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2195	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2198	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2202	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.94.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2203	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.101.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2204	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2205	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	DOM43_bin.70.fa	p__Verrucomicrobiota ;g__Moanabacter;s__
2206	DOM43	Aciculites cribrophora	-	-
2232	Pf10,Pf11,Pf12,Pf6,Pf7,Pf8,Pf9	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf9_bin.7.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Bin55;s__
2239	Pf10,Pf11,Pf5,Pf6,Pf7,Pf9	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf11_bin.50.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Bin65;s__

2258	Pf10,Pf12	Petrocia ficiformis	-,Pf4_bin.35.fa	- ,p__Proteobacteria;g__ _Porisulfidus;s__
2270	Pf10,Pf11,Pf4,Pf5,Pf6,Pf7, Pf8	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf5_bin.30.fa	p__Verrucomicrobiota ;g__UBA2970;s__
2299	Pf10,Pf11,Pf12,Pf6,Pf7,Pf 8,Pf9	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf9_bin.7.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Bin55;s__
2218	Pf10	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2332	Pf10,Pf7,gb278	Petrocia ficiformis,Geodia barretti CAN	Pf10_bin.11.fa,gb5_2_bin.68.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2225	Pf10	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2226	Pf10,Pf6	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2227	Pf10	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2273	Pf10,Pf11,Pf12,Pf4	Petrocia ficiformis	-,Pf4_bin.36.fa	-,p__Cyanobacteria;g__ _Aphanocapsa;s__Aph anocapsa feldmannii
2230	Pf10	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2238	Pf11,Pf7,Pf8	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf7_bin.23.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2366	Pf11,Pf4,Pf5,Pf6,Pf7,Pf8,P f9	Petrocia ficiformis	-,Pf7_bin.64.fa	-,p__Actinobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2362	Pf11,Pf7,Pf8,Pf9	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf7_bin.5.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ ;s__
2248	Pf11	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2259	Pf12	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf11_bin.25.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__B in22;s__
2261	Pf12	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf10_bin.11.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2265	Pf4	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2266	Pf4	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf4_bin.61.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Bin36;s__

2268	Pf4	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf4_bin.61.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__Bin36;s__
2278	Pf4	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf7_bin.54.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__s__
2282	Pf4,Pf6,Pf8	Petrocia ficiformis	-,Pf4_bin.33.fa	- ,p__Acidobacteriota;g__UBA8438;s__
2283	Pf4	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf4_bin.4.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__GCA-2724215;s__
2345	Pf5,Pf6,Pf7,Pf8	Petrocia ficiformis	-,Pf7_bin.19.fa	- ,p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
2296	Pf5,gb3_2,gb8_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR,Petrocia ficiformis,Geodia atlantica	-,gb1_bin.4.fa	- ,p__Latescibacterota;g__GCA-2724215;s__
2297	Pf5	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf7_bin.23.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__s__
2328	Pf7,Pf8	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2330	Pf7	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf9_bin.53.fa	p__Gemmatimonadota;g__Bin94;s__
2334	Pf7	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf11_bin.25.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__Bin22;s__
2356	Pf8	Petrocia ficiformis	-	-
2367	Pf9	Petrocia ficiformis	Pf9_bin.54.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__UBA8231;s__
2522	gb10,gb1,gb2_2,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb5_2,gb6,gb7,gb8_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia atlantica	gb5_2_bin.9.fa,-	p__Acidobacteriota;g__UBA8438;s__,-
2468	gb10,gb126,gb1,gb278,gb2_2,gb305,gb7,gb8_2	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia barretti CAN	-,gb126_bin.26.fa	- ,p__Acidobacteriota;g__s__
2609	gb10,gb2_2,gb6,gb8_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-

2380	gb10,gb7	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-
2527	gb10,gb2_2,gb5_2,gb7	Geodia barretti NOR	-,gb4_2_bin.25.fa	,p__Poribacteria;g__; s__
2510	gb10,gb126,gb1,gb278,gb305,gb4_2	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia barretti CAN	-,gb126_bin.18.fa	,p__Acidobacteriota;g__; s__
2484	gb10,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb8_2	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia atlantica	-	-
2389	gb10	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-
2620	gb10_f,gb1_f,gb3_f,gb5_6_f,gb9_f	Seawater ATL	gb3_f_bin.30.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ REDSEA-S09-B13;s__ REDSEA-S09-B13 sp002456995
2391	gb10_f,gb1_f,gb2_f,gb5_6_f	Seawater ATL	gb3_f_bin.12.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ UBA9145;s__
2621	gb10_f,gb1_f,gb2_f,gb3_f,gb5_6_f,gb9_f	Seawater ATL	gb10_f_bin.35.fa,-	p__Proteobacteria;g__ s__,-
2495	gb10_f,gb1_f,gb2_f,gb3_f,gb5_6_f,gb9_f	Seawater ATL	gb9_f_bin.12.fa,-	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Thioglobus;s__ Thioglobus singularis,-
2426	gb10_f,gb1_f,gb5_6_f,gb9_f	Seawater ATL	gb10_f_bin.30.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ HTCC2207;s__ HTCC2207 sp002685195
2463	gb10_f,gb2_f,gb5_6_f	Seawater ATL	-,gb5_6_f_bin.55.fa	,p__Verrucomicrobiota;g__ EC70;s__
2396	gb10_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2399	gb10_f,gb2_f,gb3_f,gb5_6_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2398	gb10_f	Seawater ATL	gb10_f_bin.64.fa	p__Latescibacterota;g__ s__
2400	gb10_f	Seawater ATL	gb10_f_bin.41.fa	p__Planctomycetota;g__ GCA-2686945;s__

2444	gb126,gb2_2,gb305	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia barretti CAN	gb5_2_bin.68.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2457	gb126,gb2_2,gb6,gb7,gb8_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia barretti CAN	-	-
2616	gb1,gb5_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-
2490	gb1,gb2_2,gb3_2,gb4_2,gb5_2,gb6,gb7	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia atlantica	-	-
2623	gb1_f,gb2_f,gb3_f,gb5_6_f,gb9_f	Seawater ATL	gb9_f_bin.17.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ UBA11791;s__
2427	gb1_f	Seawater ATL	gb1_f_bin.23.fa	p__Actinobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2428	gb1_f,gb2_f,gb3_f	Seawater ATL	gb1_f_bin.29.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ GCA-2726415;s__
2431	gb278,gb305,gb5_2,gb6	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia barretti CAN	gb278_bin.34.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2435	gb278	Geodia barretti CAN	gb305_bin.51.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ ;s__
2437	gb278	Geodia barretti CAN	-	-
2518	gb2_2,gb305,gb4_2,gb6,gb8_2,gb9	Geodia barretti NOR,Geodia barretti CAN	-,gb278_bin.45.fa	-,p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2519	gb2_2,gb4_2,gb6,gb8_2	Geodia barretti NOR	gb6_bin.52.fa	p__Acidobacteriota;g__ _Bin61;s__
2466	gb2_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2467	gb2_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2471	gb305	Geodia barretti CAN	gb305_bin.15.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2479	gb3_2	Geodia atlantica	gb4_2_bin.48.fa	p__Poribacteria;g__M SPOR6;s__
2486	gb3_2	Geodia atlantica	-	-
2489	gb3_2	Geodia atlantica	-	-
2491	gb3_2	Geodia atlantica	-	-
2493	gb3_f	Seawater ATL	-	-

2500	gb3_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2514	gb4_2	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-
2516	gb4_2	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-
2520	gb4_2	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-
2525	gb5_2	Geodia barretti NOR	gb2_2_bin.49.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2538	gb5_6_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2547	gb5_6_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2548	gb5_6_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2550	gb5_6_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2551	gb5_6_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2555	gb6	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-
2577	gb7	Geodia barretti NOR	-	-
2619	gb9_f	Seawater ATL	gb9_f_bin.8.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Methylobacterium;s__ Methylobacterium sp900112625
2625	gb9_f	Seawater ATL	gb5_6_f_bin.38.fa	p__Chloroflexota;g__ UBA11795;s__
2627	gb9_f	Seawater ATL	-	-
2630	sw_7,sw_8,sw_9	Seawater MED	sw_7_bin.7.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ Henriciella;s__Henrici ella sp002172915
2629	sw_7,sw_8,sw_9	Seawater MED	sw_9_bin.6.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ ;s__
2631	sw_8	Seawater MED	-	-
2633	sw_8	Seawater MED	sw_9_bin.8.fa	p__Proteobacteria;g__ UBA8309;s__UBA8309 sp002457765

Table S3.2. Description of connected components featuring included gene cluster families (GCFs) and representative GCF.

CC	GCFs	Reps
A	2249, 2410, 2286, 2173, 2519	2410, 2286
E	2402, 1911	2402
K	1896, 2043, 2281, 1903	2043
H	2559, 2044, 2282	2559
R	1912, 2027, 2255	1912
C	1892, 2553	1892
B	2002, 2039, 2506, 2549, 2508, 2036, 2345, 2468, 2510, 2457	2002, 2039
D	1983, 2009, 2362	1983
F	1823, 1918, 2325, 2296	2325
J	1854, 1884	1884
I	1886, 2554	2554
P	2045, 2138	2138
G	2270	2270
O	2526	2526
M	2557, 2527	2557
T	2484, 2616	2484
L	2010	2010
N	2522	2522
Q	2609	2609
S	2366	2366

Table S4. Detailed BGC gene annotations

Table S4.1. Description of ORF borders for BGCs displayed in Figure 1.

Contig	GCF	CC	Start ORF	Stop ORF
Pf12_c00118	2286	A	1	34
gb1_c01994	2410	A	1	12
gb5_2_c00041	2402	E	10	25
Pf12_c00284	2043	K	17	24
Pf11_c00818	2559	H	12	22
DOM045_c00026	1912	R	10	24
DOM007B_c00243	1892	C	1	21
DOM045_c00004	2002	B	15	25
DOM016_c00717	2039	B	19	31
DOM044_c00402	1983	D	5	24
Pf7_c00820	2325	F	12	27
DOM43_c00257	1884	J	13	27
gb4_2_c00117	2554	I	3	20
DOM026_c00344	2138	P	7	22
Pf8_c00244	2270	G	12	24
DOM14B_c00569	2526	O	1	26
gb4_2_c02126	2557	M	1	10
gb3_2_c07789	2484	T	1	7
DOM057_c01231	2010	L	11	26
gb4_2_c00127	2522	N	2	17
gb9_c09452	2609	Q	1	6
Pf7_c00139	2366	S	13	19

Table S4.2.antiSMASH annotations of contig Pf12_c00118, detected in GCF 2286 and CC A

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF01979.22 (Amidohydrolase family) PF01979.22: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity	
2	SMCOG1065:ABC-2 type transporter	PF01061.26 (ABC-2 type transporter) PF01061.26: GO:0016020: membrane	transporter
3	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding	transporter
4	SMCOG1293:aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase	PF01315.24 (Aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase, a/b hammerhead domain) PF02738.20 (Molybdopterin-binding domain of aldehyde dehydrogenase) PF02738.20: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF02738.20: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
5		PF01850.23 (PIN domain)	
6		PF01402.23 (Ribbon-helix-helix protein, copG family) PF01402.23: GO:0006355: regulation of transcription, DNA-templated	
7		PF01145.27 (SPFH domain / Band 7 family) PF16200.7 (C-terminal region of band_7)	
8		PF01957.20 (NfeD-like C-terminal, partner-binding)	
9		PF05063.16 (MethylTransferase-A70)	
10	SMCOG1168:O-succinylhomoserine sulfhydrylase	PF01053.22 (Cys/Met metabolism PLP-dependent enzyme) PF01053.22: GO:0030170: pyridoxal phosphate binding PF01053.22: GO:0019346: transsulfuration	biosynthetic-additional
11		PF01242.21 (6-pyruvoyl tetrahydropterin synthase)	

12		-	
13	SMCOG1034:cytochrome P450	PF00067.24 (Cytochrome P450) PF00067.24: GO:0005506: iron ion binding PF00067.24: GO:0016705: oxidoreductase activity, acting on paired donors, with incorporation or reduction of molecular oxygen PF00067.24: GO:0020037: heme binding PF00067.24: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000678.1, sav_2999, Streptomyces avermitilis, Terpene, pentalenolactone
14		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
15	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001465.1, bmp2, Marinomonas mediterranea MMB-1, Other, bromopyrroles/bromophenols
16	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF13193.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000649.1, fadD, Streptomyces griseus, Terpene, carotenoid
17		PF06983.15 (3-demethylubiquinone-9 3-methyltransferase)	
18		PF09365.12 (Conserved hypothetical protein (DUF2461)) TIGR02453 (TIGR02453: TIGR02453 family protein)	
19		-	
20		PF02544.18 (3-oxo-5-alpha-steroid 4-dehydrogenase) PF02544.18: GO:0016627: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors PF02544.18: GO:0006629: lipid metabolic process	

21	SMCOG1010:NAD-dependent epimerase/dehydratase	PF01370.23 (NAD dependent epimerase/dehydratase family) PF01370.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity	biosynthetic-additional
22	SMCOG1240:riboflavin biosynthesis protein RibD	PF00383.25 (Cytidine and deoxycytidylate deaminase zinc-binding region)	biosynthetic-additional
23		PF00291.27 (Pyridoxal-phosphate dependent enzyme) (PLP-dependent enzymes superfamily represented by the beta subunit of tryptophan synthase) TIGR01274 (ACC_deam: 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate deaminase)	
24	SMCOG1036:alpha/beta hydrolase fold protein	PF00561.22 (alpha/beta hydrolase fold)	biosynthetic-additional
25	SMCOG1001:short-chain dehydrogenase/reductase SDR	PF00106.27 (short chain dehydrogenase) PF00106.27: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0001895.1, 11105, Streptomyces sp., Polyketide huanglongmycin
26		PF01588.22 (Putative tRNA binding domain) (This domain may perform a common function in tRNA aminoacylation) PF01588.22: GO:0000049: tRNA binding	
27		PF07676.14 (WD40-like Beta Propeller Repeat) PF14684.8 (Tricorn protease C1 domain) PF03572.20 (Peptidase family S41) PF03572.20: GO:0008236: serine-type peptidase activity PF03572.20: GO:0006508: proteolysis	biosynthetic-additional
28		PF00916.22 (Sulfate permease family) PF01740.23 (STAS domain) PF00916.22: GO:0015116: sulfate transmembrane transporter activity	

		PF00916.22: GO:0008272: sulfate transport PF00916.22: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane	
29		PF01244.23 (Membrane dipeptidase (Peptidase family M19)) PF01244.23: GO:0070573: metallodipeptidase activity PF01244.23: GO:0006508: proteolysis	
30		PF02574.18 (Homocysteine S-methyltransferase)	
31		-	
32		-	

Table S4.3. antiSMASH annotations of contig gb1_c01994, detected in GCF 02410 and CC A

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF13193.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000649.1, fadD, Streptomyces griseus, Terpene, carotenoid
2	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001831.1, MXAN_6635, Myxococcus xanthus, Polyketide, alkylpyrones
3		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
4	SMCOG1034:cytochrome P450	PF00067.24 (Cytochrome P450) PF00067.24: GO:0005506: iron ion binding PF00067.24: GO:0016705: oxidoreductase activity, acting on paired donors, with incorporation or reduction of molecular oxygen PF00067.24: GO:0020037: heme binding	biosynthetic-additional p450 (11..429): active site cysteine inconclusive MiBIG:BGC0001811.1, tri11, Fusarium asiaticum, Terpene, trichodiene-11-one

		PF00067.24: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
5	SMCOG1034:cytochrome P450	PF00067.24 (Cytochrome P450) PF00067.24: GO:0005506: iron ion binding PF00067.24: GO:0016705: oxidoreductase activity, acting on paired donors, with incorporation or reduction of molecular oxygen PF00067.24: GO:0020037: heme binding PF00067.24: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional p450 (6..425): active site cysteine inconclusive MiBIG: BGC0000675.1, SSCG_3690, Streptomyces clavuligerus ATCC 27064, Terpene, (+)-T-muurolol
6	SMCOG1034:cytochrome P450	PF00067.24 (Cytochrome P450) PF00067.24: GO:0005506: iron ion binding PF00067.24: GO:0016705: oxidoreductase activity, acting on paired donors, with incorporation or reduction of molecular oxygen PF00067.24: GO:0020037: heme binding PF00067.24: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional p450 (2..402): active site cysteine inconclusive MiBIG: BGC0001910.1, cldC, Streptomyces cyslabdanicus, Terpene, cyslabdan
7		-	
8		PF01242.21 (6-pyruvoyl tetrahydropterin synthase)	
9	SMCOG1168:O-succinylhomoserine sulfhydrylase	PF01053.22 (Cys/Met metabolism PLP-dependent enzyme) PF01053.22: GO:0030170: pyridoxal phosphate binding PF01053.22: GO:0019346: transsulfuration	biosynthetic-additional
10		PF05063.16 (MT-A70)	
11		PF01957.20 (NfeD-like C-terminal, partner-binding)	
12		PF01145.27 (SPFH domain / Band 7 family) PF16200.7 (C-terminal region of band_7)	

Table S4.4. antiSMASH annotations of contig gb5_2_c00041, detected in GCF 2402 and CC E

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
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1	SMCOG1210:glycerol kinase	PF00370.23 (FGGY family of carbohydrate kinases, N-terminal domain) PF02782.18 (FGGY family of carbohydrate kinases, C-terminal domain) PF00370.23: GO:0016773: phosphotransferase activity, alcohol group as acceptor PF00370.23: GO:0005975: carbohydrate metabolic process PF02782.18: GO:0016773: phosphotransferase activity, alcohol group as acceptor PF02782.18: GO:0005975: carbohydrate metabolic process	biosynthetic-additional
2		-	
3		PF01259.20 (SAICAR synthetase/ligase)	
4		-	
5		PF05721.15 (Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase (PhyH))	
6		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
7		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
8		PF00501 (AMP-binding)	biosynthetic-additional
9		PF13173.8 (AAA domain, ATPases) PF13635.8 (Domain of unknown function (DUF4143))	
10	SMCOG1017:aldehyde dehydrogenase	PF00171.24 (Aldehyde dehydrogenase family) PF00171.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00171.24: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
11		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
12		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	

13		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
14	SMCOG1051:TonB-dependent siderophore receptor	PF07715.17 (TonB-dependent Receptor Plug Domain) PF00593.26 (TonB dependent receptor) TIGR01783 (TonB-siderophor: TonB-dependent siderophore receptor)	transport
15		PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000889.1, fevW, Streptomyces sp. WK-5344, Other, bagremycins
16	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF01494.21 (FAD binding domain) PF01494.21: GO:0071949: FAD binding	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001366.1, orf12, Streptomyces sp. FJS31-2, Polyketide, zunyimycin
17	SMCOG1045:glycosyl transferase group 1	PF13439.8 (Glycosyltransferase Family 4) PF00534.22 (Glycosyl transferases group 1) PF00534.22: GO:0016757: transferase activity, transferring glycosyl groups	biosynthetic-additional
18			-
19		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
20	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding	Transport MiBIG: BGC0001526.1, brtI, Synechocystis salina LEGE 06099, Other, bartolosides
21		PF12704.9 (MacB-like periplasmic core domain) PF02687.23 (FtsX-like permease family) PF02687.23: GO:0016020: membrane	
22		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	

23		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
24		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family, TAXI family of the substrate-binding proteins)	
25		PF06808.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporter, DctM component) TIGR02123 (TRAP_fused: TRAP transporter, 4TM/12TM fusion protein)	
26		PF16332.7 (Domain of unknown function (DUF4962)) PF07940.15 (Heparinase II/III-like protein) PF07940.15: GO:0016829: lyase activity	
27		-	
28		PF00884.25 (Sulfatase) PF00884.25: GO:0008484: sulfuric ester hydrolase activity	
29		PF06134.13 (L-rhamnose isomerase (RhaA)) TIGR01748 (rhaA: L-rhamnose isomerase)	
30		PF05721.15 (Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase (PhyH))	
31		PF05721.15 (Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase (PhyH))	
32		-	

Table S4.5. antiSMASH annotations of contig Pf12_c00284, detected in GCF 2043 and CC K

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1	SMCOG1079:oxidoreductase	PF01408.24 (Oxidoreductase family, NAD-binding Rossmann fold) PF02894.19 (Oxidoreductase family, C-terminal alpha/beta domain) PF01408.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity	biosynthetic-additional
2	SMCOG1079:oxidoreductase	PF01408.24 (Oxidoreductase family, NAD-binding Rossmann fold) PF02894.19 (Oxidoreductase family, C-terminal alpha/beta domain)	biosynthetic-additional

		PF01408.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity	
3		-	
4		PF01220.21 (Dehydroquinase class II) TIGR01088 (aroQ: 3-dehydroquinone hydratase, type II) PF01220.21: GO:0003855: 3-dehydroquinone hydratase activity	
5	SMCOG1056: DegT/DnrJ/EryC1/StrS aminotransferase	PF01041.19 (DegT/DnrJ/EryC1/StrS aminotransferase family)	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000719.1, alloG, Streptoalloteichus hindustanus, Saccharide, tobramycin
6		-	
7		PF09924.11 (Phosphatidylglycerol lysyltransferase, C-terminal) (transfer of a lysyl group from L-lysyl-tRNA(Lys) to membrane-bound phosphatidylglycerol (PG))	
8		PF04263.18 (Thiamin pyrophosphokinase, catalytic domain) PF04263.18: GO:0004788: thiamine diphosphokinase activity PF04263.18: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF04263.18: GO:0009229: thiamine diphosphate biosynthetic process	
9	SMCOG1081:cysteine synthase	PF00291.27 (Pyridoxal-phosphate dependent enzyme)	biosynthetic-additional
10		-	
11		PF00571.30 (CBS domain, bind ligands with an adenosyl group, AMP, ATP and S-AdoMe)	(regulatory)
12		PF00571.30 (CBS domain, bind ligands with an adenosyl group, AMP, ATP and S-AdoMe)	(regulatory)
13		PF01558.20 (Pyruvate ferredoxin/ferredoxin oxidoreductase)	

		<p>PF01855.21 (Pyruvate flavodoxin/ferredoxin oxidoreductase, thiamine diP-bdg)</p> <p>PF17147.6 (Pyruvate:ferredoxin oxidoreductase core domain II)</p> <p>TIGR03710 (OAF0_sf: 2-oxoacid:acceptor oxidoreductase, alpha subunit)</p> <p>PF01558.20: GO:0016903: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the aldehyde or oxo group of donors</p> <p>PF01558.20: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p> <p>PF01855.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity</p> <p>PF01855.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p>	
14		<p>PF02775.23 (Thiamine pyrophosphate enzyme, C-terminal TPP binding domain)</p> <p>TIGR02177 (PorB_KorB: 2-oxoacid:acceptor oxidoreductase, beta subunit, pyruvate/2-ketoisovalerate family)</p> <p>PF02775.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity</p> <p>PF02775.23: GO:0030976: thiamine pyrophosphate binding</p>	<p>MiBIG: BGC0000131.1, dox5, Streptomyces sp., Polyketide, pyrrolomycin</p>
15		<p>PF04951.15 (D-aminopeptidase)</p>	
16		<p>PF13385.8 (Concanavalin A-like lectin/glucanases superfamily)</p>	
17		<p>PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase)</p> <p>PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity</p> <p>PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding</p> <p>PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p>	<p>MiBIG: BGC0000897.1, dhpG, Streptomyces luridus, Other, dehydrophos</p>
18		<p>PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)</p> <p>PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain)</p> <p>PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain)</p>	
19		<p>PF01947.18 (p-hydroxybenzoic acid synthase (chorismate lyase), DUF98)</p>	<p>biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000891.1, pl2ta16_1240/bmp6, Pseudoalteromonas</p>

			luteoviolacea, Other (Aminocoumarin), pentabromopseudilin
20		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF06969.18 (HemN C-terminal domain) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
21		PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000889.1, fevW, Streptomyces sp., Other, bagremycins
22	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001831.1,, MXAN_6635, Myxococcus xanthus, Polyketide, alkylpyrone
23		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family, TAXI family of the substrate-binding proteins) TIGR02122 (TRAP_TAXI: TRAP transporter solute receptor, TAXI family)	
24		PF05193.23 (Peptidase M16 inactive domain) PF08367.13 (Peptidase M16C associated) PF08367.13: GO:0006508: proteolysis	biosynthetic-additional
25		PF00712.21 (DNA polymerase III beta subunit, N-terminal domain) PF02767.18 (DNA polymerase III beta subunit, central domain) PF02768.17 (DNA polymerase III beta subunit, C-terminal domain) TIGR00663 (dnan: DNA polymerase III, beta subunit) PF00712.21: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF00712.21: GO:0003887: DNA-directed DNA polymerase activity PF00712.21: GO:0008408: 3'-5' exonuclease activity PF00712.21: GO:0006260: DNA replication PF00712.21: GO:0009360: DNA polymerase III complex	

		<p>PF02767.18: GO:0003887: DNA-directed DNA polymerase activity PF02767.18: GO:0008408: 3'-5' exonuclease activity PF02767.18: GO:0006260: DNA replication PF02767.18: GO:0009360: DNA polymerase III complex PF02768.17: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF02768.17: GO:0003887: DNA-directed DNA polymerase activity PF02768.17: GO:0008408: 3'-5' exonuclease activity PF02768.17: GO:0006260: DNA replication PF02768.17: GO:0009360: DNA polymerase III complex</p>	
26	SMCOG1272:TPR repeat-containing protein	<p>PF13432.8 (Tetratricopeptide repeat) PF00515.30 (Tetratricopeptide repeat) PF13432.8 (Tetratricopeptide repeat) PF00515.30: GO:0005515: protein binding</p>	other
27		<p>PF11412.10 (Disulphide bond corrector protein DsbC - transmembrane electron transporter) PF02683.17 (Cytochrome C biogenesis protein transmembrane region) PF03190.17 (Protein of unknown function, DUF255) PF02683.17: GO:0017004: cytochrome complex assembly PF02683.17: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF02683.17: GO:0016020: membrane</p>	
28		<p>PF08665.14 (PglZ domain, putative phosphatase)</p>	
29	SMCOG1261:hypothetical protein	<p>PF01565.25 (FAD binding domain) PF02913.21 (FAD linked oxidases, C-terminal domain) PF01565.25: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF01565.25: GO:0050660: flavin adenine dinucleotide binding PF01565.25: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF02913.21: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF02913.21: GO:0050660: flavin adenine dinucleotide binding</p>	other

30		-	
31		-	
32	SMCOG1261:hypothetical protein	PF01565.25 (FAD binding domain) PF02913.21 (FAD linked oxidases, C-terminal domain) PF01565.25: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF01565.25: GO:0050660: flavin adenine dinucleotide binding PF01565.25: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF02913.21: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF02913.21: GO:0050660: flavin adenine dinucleotide binding	other
33		PF13385.8 (Concanavalin A-like lectin/glucanases superfamily)	
34		-	
35	SMCOG1049:AcrB/AcrD/AcrF family protein	PF00873.21 (AcrB/AcrD/AcrF family) PF00873.21: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF00873.21: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00873.21: GO:0016020: membrane	transport
36		PF00873.21 (AcrB/AcrD/AcrF family) PF00873.21: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF00873.21: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00873.21: GO:0016020: membrane	

Table S4.6. antiSMASH annotations of contig Pf11_c00818, detected in GCF 2559 and CC H

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF03993.14 (Domain of Unknown Function (DUF349))	
2		PF00160.23 (Cyclophilin type peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase/CLD) PF00160.23: GO:0003755: peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase activity PF00160.23: GO:0000413: protein peptidyl-prolyl isomerization	

3		PF00160.23 (Cyclophilin type peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase/CLD) PF00160.23: GO:0003755: peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase activity PF00160.23: GO:0000413: protein peptidyl-prolyl isomerization	
4	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00550.27 (Phosphopantetheine attachment site) PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF01553.23 (Acyltransferase) PF01553.23: GO:0016746: transferase activity, transferring acyl groups	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001831.1, MXAN_6636, Myxococcus xanthus DK 1622, Polyketide, alkylpyrone
5	SMCOG1040:alcohol dehydrogenase	PF08240.14 (Alcohol dehydrogenase GroES-like domain) PF00107.28 (Zinc-binding dehydrogenase) PF00107.28: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF08240.14: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
6		PF00583.27 (Acetyltransferase (GNAT) family) PF00583.27: GO:0008080: N-acetyltransferase activity	
7	SMCOG1168:O-succinylhomoserine sulfhydrylase	PF01053.22 (Cys/Met metabolism PLP-dependent enzyme) PF01053.22: GO:0030170: pyridoxal phosphate binding PF01053.22: GO:0019346: transsulfuration	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000783.1, metB, Xanthomonas oryzae, Saccharide, O-antigen
8	SMCOG1086:MATE efflux family protein	PF01554.20 (MatE) TIGR00797 (matE: MATE efflux family protein) PF01554.20: GO:0015297: antiporter activity PF01554.20: GO:0042910: xenobiotic transmembrane transporter activity PF01554.20: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF01554.20: GO:0016020: membrane	transport
9		PF00293.30 (NUDIX domain) PF00293.30: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity	
10		PF00521.22 (DNA gyrase/topoisomerase IV, subunit A)	

		<p>PF03989.15 (DNA gyrase C-terminal domain, beta-propeller) PF00521.22: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF00521.22: GO:0003918: DNA topoisomerase type II (double strand cut, ATP-hydrolyzing) activity PF00521.22: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00521.22: GO:0006265: DNA topological change PF03989.15: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF03989.15: GO:0003916: DNA topoisomerase activity PF03989.15: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF03989.15: GO:0006265: DNA topological change</p>	
11		<p>PF02518.28 (Histidine kinase-, DNA gyrase B-, and HSP90-like ATPase) PF00204.27 (DNA gyrase B) PF01751.24 (Toprim domain) PF00986.23 (DNA gyrase B subunit, carboxyl terminus) PF00204.27: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF00204.27: GO:0003918: DNA topoisomerase type II (double strand cut, ATP-hydrolyzing) activity PF00204.27: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00204.27: GO:0006265: DNA topological change PF00986.23: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF00986.23: GO:0003918: DNA topoisomerase type II (double strand cut, ATP-hydrolyzing) activity PF00986.23: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00986.23: GO:0006265: DNA topological change</p>	
12		<p>PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain) PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)</p>	
13		<p>PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding</p>	biosynthetic-additional
14	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic

			MiBiG:BGC0000891, pl2ta16_1236/bmp2, Pseudoalteromonas luteoviolacea, Other (Aminocoumarin), pentabromopseudilin
15		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
16		PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBiG:BGC0000889.1, fevW, Streptomyces sp. Other, bagremycins
17		PF00903.27 (Glyoxalase/Bleomycin resistance protein/Dioxygenase superfamily)	
18		PF01593.26 (Flavin containing amine oxidoreductase) PF01593.26: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF01593.26: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	(biosynthetic)
19		PF00034.23 (Cytochrome c) PF00034.23: GO:0009055: electron transfer activity PF00034.23: GO:0020037: heme binding	
20		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family) TIGR02122 (TRAP_TAXI: TRAP transporter solute receptor, TAXI family)	
21		PF06808.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporter, DctM component) TIGR02123 (TRAP_fused: TRAP transporter, 4TM/12TM fusion protein)	
22		PF00860.22 (Permease family) PF00860.22: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF00860.22: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00860.22: GO:0016020: membrane	

23		PF07045.13 (Domain of unknown function (DUF1330))	
24		-	
25		PF13173.8 (AAA domain) PF13635.8 (Domain of unknown function (DUF4143))	
26		PF01597.21 (Glycine cleavage H-protein) (H-protein shuttles the methylamine group of glycine)	
27		-	
28	SMCOG1178:cobalamin synthesis protein/P47K family protein	PF02492.21 (CobW/HypB/UreG, nucleotide-binding domain)	biosynthetic-additional

Table S4.7. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM045_c00026, detected in GCF 1912 and CC R

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		-	
2	SMCOG1272:TPR repeat-containing protein	PF13414.8 (TPR repeat)	Other
3	SMCOG1255:cold-shock DNA-binding domain protein	PF00313.24 ('Cold-shock' DNA-binding domain) PF00313.24: GO:0003676: nucleic acid binding	regulatory
4		-	
5	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding	transport
6	SMCOG1096:polar amino acid ABC transporter, inner membrane	PF00528.24 (Binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component) TIGR01726 (HEQRo_perm_3TM: amino ABC transporter, permease protein, 3-TM region, His/Glu/Gln/Arg/opine family)	transport

		PF00528.24: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00528.24: GO:0016020: membrane	
7	SMCOG1096:polar amino acid ABC transporter, inner membrane	PF00528.24 (Binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component) TIGR01726 (HEQRo_perm_3TM: amino ABC transporter, permease protein, 3-TM region, His/Glu/Gln/Arg/opine family) PF00528.24: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00528.24: GO:0016020: membrane	transport
8	SMCOG1091:glutamine-binding lipoprotein glnH	PF00497.22 (Bacterial extracellular solute-binding proteins, family 3)	biosynthetic-additional
9		PF05833.13 (NFACT N-terminal and middle domains) PF05670.15 (NFACT protein RNA binding domain)	
10	SMCOG1214:binding-protein-dependent transport systems	PF00528.24 (Binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component) PF00528.24 (Binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component) PF00528.24: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00528.24: GO:0016020: membrane	transport
11		-	
12		-	
13		-	
14		PF00941.23 (FAD binding domain in molybdopterin dehydrogenase) PF03450.19 (CO dehydrogenase flavoprotein C-terminal domain) PF00941.23: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00941.23: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
15		PF00111.29 (2Fe-2S iron-sulfur cluster binding domain) PF01799.22 ([2Fe-2S] binding domain)	

		<p>PF00111.29: GO:0009055: electron transfer activity PF00111.29: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding PF01799.22: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF01799.22: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF01799.22: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p>	
16	SMCOG1293:aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase	<p>PF01315.24 (Aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase, a/b hammerhead domain) PF02738.20 (Molybdopterin-binding domain of aldehyde dehydrogenase) PF02738.20: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF02738.20: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p>	biosynthetic-additional
17		-	
18	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	<p>PF16177.7 (Acetyl-coenzyme A synthetase N-terminus) PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF13193.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)</p>	biosynthetic
19		PF01571.23 (Aminomethyltransferase folate-binding domain)	
20		<p>PF13510.8 (2Fe-2S iron-sulfur cluster binding domain) PF07992.16 (Pyridine nucleotide-disulphide oxidoreductase) PF17806.3 (Sarcosine oxidase A3 domain) PF01571.23 (Aminomethyltransferase folate-binding domain) PF08669.13 (Glycine cleavage T-protein C-terminal barrel domain) PF07992.16: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF07992.16: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p>	
21		<p>PF04267.14 (Sarcosine oxidase, delta subunit family) PF04267.14: GO:0008115: sarcosine oxidase activity PF04267.14: GO:0046653: tetrahydrofolate metabolic process</p>	
22	SMCOG1103:FAD dependent oxidoreductase	<p>PF01266.26 (FAD dependent oxidoreductase) PF01266.26: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity</p>	(biosynthetic)

		PF01266.26: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
23		PF05721.15 (Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase (PhyH))	
24		PF12228.10 (Protein of unknown function (DUF3604))	
25	SMCOG1268:mandelate racemase/muconate lactonizing enzyme	PF02746.18 (Mandelate racemase / muconate lactonizing enzyme, N-terminal domain) PF13378.8 (Enolase C-terminal domain-like)	biosynthetic-additional
26	SMCOG1268:mandelate racemase/muconate lactonizing enzyme	PF13378.8 (Enolase C-terminal domain-like)	biosynthetic-additional
27		PF01261.26 (Xylose isomerase-like TIM barrel)	
28		PF03447.18 (Homoserine dehydrogenase, NAD binding domain) PF00742.21 (Homoserine dehydrogenase) PF01842.27 (ACT domain) PF00742.21: GO:0006520: cellular amino acid metabolic process PF00742.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF03447.18: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF03447.18: GO:0050661: NADP binding PF03447.18: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
29		PF00291.27 (Pyridoxal-phosphate dependent enzyme) TIGR00260 (thrC: threonine synthase): [8:326](score: 320.5, e-value: 3.1e-96)	
30		PF00696.30 (Amino acid kinase family) PF01842.27 (ACT domain) PF13840.8 (ACT domain) TIGR00657 (asp_kinases: aspartate kinase) TIGR00656 (asp_kin_monofn: aspartate kinase, monofunctional class)	

31		PF02620.19 (Large ribosomal RNA subunit accumulation protein YceD)	
32		PF01783.25 (Ribosomal L32p protein family) TIGR01031 (rpmF_bact: ribosomal protein bL32) PF01783.25: GO:0003735: structural constituent of ribosome PF01783.25: GO:0006412: translation PF01783.25: GO:0015934: large ribosomal subunit	
33	SMCOG1084:3-oxoacyl-(acyl carrier protein) synthase III	PF08545.12 (3-Oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein (ACP)] synthase III) PF08541.12 (3-Oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein (ACP)] synthase III C terminal) TIGR00747 (fabH: 3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] synthase III) PF08545.12: GO:0004315: 3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] synthase activity PF08545.12: GO:0006633: fatty acid biosynthetic process	biosynthetic-additional
34	SMCOG1021:malonyl CoA-acyl carrier protein transacylase	PF00698.23 (Acyl transferase domain) TIGR00128 (fabD: malonyl CoA-acyl carrier protein transacylase)	biosynthetic-additional PKS_AT (18..303) (Methyl)Malonyl-CoA specificity inconclusive found active site serine: True, scaffold matched GHGE: True
35	SMCOG1001:short-chain dehydrogenase/reductase SDR	PF13561.8 (Enoyl-(Acyl carrier protein) reductase) TIGR01830 (3oxo_ACP_reduc: 3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] reductase)	biosynthetic-additional PKS_KR (6..179) KR domain putatively catalyzing D-configuration product formation catalytic triad S,Y,N inconclusive
36		PF00550.27 (Phosphopantetheine attachment site) TIGR00517 (acyl_carrier: acyl carrier protein)	biosynthetic-additional
37	SMCOG1022:Beta-ketoacyl synthase	PF00109.28 (Beta-ketoacyl synthase, N-terminal domain) PF02801.24 (Beta-ketoacyl synthase, C-terminal domain)	biosynthetic-additional PKS_KS (6..411)

		TIGR03150 (fabF: beta-ketoacyl-acyl-carrier-protein synthase II)	found active site cysteine: True, scaffold matched GSSS: False found active site histidines: True
38		-	
39	SMCOG1013:aminotransferase class-III	PF00202.23 (Aminotransferase class-III) PF00202.23: GO:0008483: transaminase activity PF00202.23: GO:0030170: pyridoxal phosphate binding	biosynthetic-additional
40		PF00903.27 (Glyoxalase/Bleomycin resistance protein/Dioxygenase superfamily)	
41		PF12704.9 (MacB-like periplasmic core domain)	
42			

Table S4.8. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM007B_c00243, detected in GCF 1892 and CC C

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1	SMCOG1082:TonB-dependent siderophore receptor family	PF13620.8 (Carboxypeptidase regulatory-like domain) PF00593.26 (TonB dependent receptor)	transport
2	SMCOG1045:glycosyl transferase group 1	PF13439.8 (Glycosyltransferase Family 4) PF00534.22 (Glycosyl transferases group 1) PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00534.22: GO:0016757: transferase activity, transferring glycosyl groups	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000487.1,cclG, Carnobacterium maltaromaticum, RiPP, carnocyclin
3		-	
4		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional

5	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	biosynthetic
6		PF13279.8 (Thioesterase-like superfamily)	
7		-	
8	MCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	biosynthetic
9		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
10		PF12705.9 (PD-(D/E)XK nuclease superfamily)	
11		PF00580.23 (UvrD/REP helicase N-terminal domain) PF13361.8 (UvrD-like helicase C-terminal domain) PF12705.9 (PD-(D/E)XK nuclease superfamily) PF00580.23: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF13361.8: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF13361.8: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity	
12		-	
13		-	
14		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF13186.8 (Iron-sulfur cluster-binding domain) PF02810.17 (SEC-C motif) TIGR03942 (sulfatase_rSAM: anaerobic sulfatase maturase) TIGR04085 (rSAM_more_4Fe4S: radical SAM additional 4Fe4S-binding SPASM domain) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
15		PF03190.17 (Protein of unknown function, DUF255) PF07221.13 (N-acylglucosamine 2-epimerase (GlcNAc 2-epimerase))	
16		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase)	

		PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
17		-	
18	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF08402.12 (TOBE domain) TIGR01187 (potA: polyamine ABC transporter, ATP-binding protein) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF08402.12: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF08402.12: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF08402.12: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF08402.12: GO:0043190: ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter complex	Transport MiBIG: BGC0001526.1, brtI, Synechocystis salina, Other, bartolosides
19		PF13416.8 (Bacterial extracellular solute-binding protein)	
20	SMCOG1067:putative ABC transporter permease protein	PF00528.24 (Binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component) PF00528.24: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00528.24: GO:0016020: membrane	transport
21	SMCOG1069:putative ABC transporter permease protein	PF00528.24 (Binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component) PF00528.24: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00528.24: GO:0016020: membrane	transport

Table S4.9. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM045_c00004, detected in GCF 2002 and CC B

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF01751.24 (Toprim domain) PF00986.23 (DNA gyrase B subunit, carboxyl terminus) PF00986.23: GO:0003677: DNA binding	

		PF00986.23: GO:0003918: DNA topoisomerase type II (double strand cut, ATP-hydrolyzing) activity PF00986.23: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00986.23: GO:0006265: DNA topological change	
2		-	
3		PF03099.21 (Biotin/lipoate A/B protein ligase family) PF03099.21: GO:0006464: cellular protein modification process	
4	SMCOG1139:aminotransferase class V	PF00266.21 (Aminotransferase class-V)	biosynthetic-additional
5		PF01597.21 (Glycine cleavage H-protein)	
6	SMCOG1178:cobalamin synthesis protein/P47K family protein	PF02492.21 (CobW/HypB/UreG, nucleotide-binding domain):	biosynthetic-additional
7		-	
8		-	
9		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
10	SMCOG1182:Polyprenyl synthetase	PF01976.19 (Protein of unknown function DUF116) PF00348.19 (Polyprenyl synthetase) PF00348.19: GO:0008299: isoprenoid biosynthetic process	biosynthetic-additional
11		PF00432.23 (Prenyltransferase and squalene oxidase repeat) PF00432.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity	
12		PF13249.8 (Squalene-hopene cyclase N-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic (terpene_cyclase)
13		PF03235.16 (Protein of unknown function DUF262)	

14		PF18735.3 (RiboL-PSP-HEPN)	
15		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
16		PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain) PF01011.23 (PQQ enzyme repeat)	
17		PF05685.14 (Putative restriction endonuclease)	
18		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
19		-	
20	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000890.1, bmp2, Pseudoalteromonas phenolica, Other (Aminocoumarin), pentabromopseudilin
21		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
22	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	biosynthetic
23		PF00903.27 (Glyoxalase/Bleomycin resistance protein/Dioxygenase superfamily)	
24		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family) TIGR02122 (TRAP_TAXI: TRAP transporter solute receptor, TAXI family)	
25		PF06808.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporter, DctM component)	

		TIGR02123 (TRAP_fused: TRAP transporter, 4TM/12TM fusion protein)	
26		PF04174.15 (A circularly permuted ATPgrasp)	
27		PF04168.14 (A predicted alpha-helical domain with a conserved ER motif.)	
28		PF00909.23 (Ammonium Transporter Family) PF00909.23: GO:0008519: ammonium transmembrane transporter activity PF00909.23: GO:0015696: ammonium transport PF00909.23: GO:0016020: membrane	
29		PF03641.16 (Possible lysine decarboxylase) TIGR00730 (TIGR00730: TIGR00730 family protein)	
30		PF01740.23 (STAS (Sulphate Transporter and AntiSigma factor antagonist) domain, TIGR00377 (ant_ant_sig: anti-anti-sigma factor)	In ecoli shown to interact with acyl carrier protein (ACP))
31		PF13581.8 (Histidine kinase-like ATPase domain)	
32		PF01740.23 (STAS domain) TIGR00377 (ant_ant_sig: anti-anti-sigma factor)	
33		PF13581.8 (Histidine kinase-like ATPase domain)	
34	SMCOG1054:hypothetical protein	PF00672.27 (HAMP domain) PF07228.14 (Stage II sporulation protein E (SpolIE)) PF00672.27: GO:0007165: signal transduction PF00672.27: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane PF07228.14: GO:0016791: phosphatase activity	Other
35		-	
36	SMCOG1122:ATP-dependent RNA helicase	PF00270.31 (DEAD/DEAH box helicase) PF00271.33 (Helicase conserved C-terminal domain)	

		PF16124.7 (RecQ zinc-binding) PF09382.12 (RQC domain) PF00570.25 (HRDC domain) TIGR01389 (recQ: ATP-dependent DNA helicase RecQ) PF00270.31: GO:0003676: nucleic acid binding PF00270.31: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00570.25: GO:0003676: nucleic acid binding PF09382.12: GO:0043138: 3'-5' DNA helicase activity PF09382.12: GO:0006260: DNA replication PF09382.12: GO:0006281: DNA repair	
37		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
38		PF02190.18 (ATP-dependent protease La (LON) substrate-binding domain)	
39	SMCOG1036:alpha/beta hydrolase fold protein	PF00561.22 (alpha/beta hydrolase fold)	biosynthetic-additional
40		-	
41		PF16313.7 (Met-zincin, This domain carries the highly characteristic met-zincin motif HExxHxxGxxH, the extended zinc-binding domain of metallopeptidases.)	
42			

Table S4.10. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM016_c00717, detected in GCF 2039 and CC B

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		-	
2		PF04306.15 (Protein of unknown function (DUF456))	
3		PF10041.11 (Uncharacterized conserved protein (DUF2277))	

4	SMCOG1268:mandelate racemase/muconate lactonizing enzyme	PF02746.18 (Mandelate racemase / muconate lactonizing enzyme, N-terminal domain) PF13378.8 (Enolase C-terminal domain-like)	biosynthetic-additional
5		PF13709.8 (Domain of unknown function (DUF4159))	
6		-	
7		PF12146.10 (Serine aminopeptidase, S33)	biosynthetic-additional (PF00561)
8		PF07978.15 (NIPSNAP, hypothetical proteins)	
9		PF00413.26 (Matrixin) PF00413.26: GO:0004222: metalloendopeptidase activity PF00413.26: GO:0008270: zinc ion binding PF00413.26: GO:0006508: proteolysis PF00413.26: GO:0031012: extracellular matrix	
10		-	
11		PF02190.18 (ATP-dependent protease La (LON) substrate-binding domain)	
12		-	
13		-	
14	SMCOG1054:hypothetical protein	PF00672.27 (HAMP domain) PF07228.14 (Stage II sporulation protein E (SpolIE)) PF00672.27: GO:0007165: signal transduction PF00672.27: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane PF07228.14: GO:0016791: phosphatase activity	MiBIG:BGC0000518.1, SSQG_07265, Streptomyces viridochromogenes, RiPP, informatipeptin
15		PF13581.8 (Histidine kinase-like ATPase domain)	
16		PF01740.23 (STAS domain) TIGR00377 (ant_ant_sig: anti-anti-sigma factor)	

17		PF00909.23 (Ammonium Transporter Family) PF00909.23: GO:0008519: ammonium transmembrane transporter activity PF00909.23: GO:0015696: ammonium transport PF00909.23: GO:0016020: membrane	
18	SMCOG1082: TonB-dependent siderophore receptor family	PF00593.26 (TonB dependent receptor)	transport
19		PF06808.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporter, DctM component) TIGR02123 (TRAP_fused: TRAP transporter, 4TM/12TM fusion protein)	
20		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family) TIGR02122 (TRAP_TAXI: TRAP transporter solute receptor, TAXI family)	
21		PF00903.27 (Glyoxalase/Bleomycin resistance protein/Dioxygenase superfamily)	
22	SMCOG1002: AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000889.1, fevW, Streptomyces sp., Other, bagremycins
23		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
24	SMCOG1119: halogenase	PF01494.21 (FAD binding domain) PF01494.21: GO:0071949: FAD binding	biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001831.1, MXAN_6635, Myxococcus xanthus, Polyketide, alkylpyrones
25		-	
26		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional

27		PF05685.14 (Putative restriction endonuclease)	MiBIG: BGC0000479.1, AED99428.1, Planktothrix agardhii, RiPP, prenylagaramides
28		PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
29		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
30		PF13564.8 (DoxX-like family, uncharacterised transmembrane proteins known as DoxX)	
31		-	

Table S4.11. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM044_c00402, detected in GCF 1983 and CC D

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF02366.20 (Dolichyl-phosphate-mannose-protein mannosyltransferase) PF14559.8 (Tetratricopeptide repeat) PF02366.20: GO:0000030: mannosyltransferase activity PF02366.20: GO:0006493: protein O-linked glycosylation PF02366.20: GO:0016020: membrane	
2	SMCOG1123:polyprenol-monophosphomannose synthase ppm1	PF00535.28 (Glycosyl transferase family 2)	biosynthetic-additional
3		PF09861.11 (Lactate racemase N-terminal domain) PF09861.11: GO:0050043: lactate racemase activity	
4		PF19501.1 (YetA-like protein) PF07944.14 (Beta-L-arabinofuranosidase, GH127)	

5	SMCOG1079:oxidoreductase	PF01408.24 (Oxidoreductase family, NAD-binding Rossmann fold) PF02894.19 (Oxidoreductase family, C-terminal alpha/beta domain) PF01408.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000720.1, tbcC (putative dehydrogenase), Streptoalloteichus tenebrarius, Saccharide, tobramycin
6	SMCOG1079:oxidoreductase	PF01408.24 (Oxidoreductase family, NAD-binding Rossmann fold) PF02894.19 (Oxidoreductase family, C-terminal alpha/beta domain) PF01408.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity	biosynthetic-additional
7		AMP-binding	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000662.1, sgr_4243(AMP), Streptomyces griseus, Terpene, grixazone
8		PF00171.24 (Aldehyde dehydrogenase family) PF00171.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00171.24: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
9		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	MiBIG: BGC0000807.1, snas_5663, Stackebrandtia nassauensis, Saccharide, phosphonoglycans
10		PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
11		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
12		PF04255.16 (Protein of unknown function (DUF433))	
13		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
14	SMCOG1051:TonB-dependent siderophore receptor	PF07715.17 (TonB-dependent Receptor Plug Domain) PF00593.26 (TonB dependent receptor)	transport

		TIGR01783 (TonB-siderophor: TonB-dependent siderophore receptor)	
15		PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	biosynthetic
16	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF01494.21 (FAD binding domain) PF01494.21: GO:0071949: FAD binding	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000837.1, vf_0841, Aliivibrio fischeri , Other, APE Vf
17	SMCOG1045:glycosyl transferase group 1	PF13579.8 (Glycosyl transferase 4-like domain) PF00534.22 (Glycosyl transferases group 1) PF00534.22: GO:0016757: transferase activity, transferring glycosyl groups	biosynthetic-additional
18		-	
19		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
20	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding	Transport MiBIG: BGC0001526.1, brtI, Synechocystis salina, Other, bartolosides
21		PF02687.23 (FtsX-like permease family) PF02687.23: GO:0016020: membrane	
22		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
23		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family) TIGR02122 (TRAP_TAXI: TRAP transporter solute receptor, TAXI family)	
24		PF06808.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporter, DctM component) TIGR02123 (TRAP_fused: TRAP transporter, 4TM/12TM fusion protein)	
25		-	
26		PF01402.23 (Ribbon-helix-helix protein, copG family)	

		PF03683.15 (Uncharacterised protein family (UPF0175)) PF01402.23: GO:0006355: regulation of transcription, DNA-templated	
27	SMCOG1059:acetyl-CoA carboxylase, carboxyl transferase	PF01039.24 (Carboxyl transferase domain)	biosynthetic-additional
28	SMCOG1189:L-carnitine dehydratase/bile acid-inducible	PF02515.19 (CoA-transferase family III) PF02515.19: GO:0008410: CoA-transferase activity	biosynthetic-additional
29		PF10282.11 (Lactonase, 7-bladed beta-propeller)	
30		PF05721.15 (Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase (PhyH))	
31		PF01261.26 (Xylose isomerase-like TIM barrel)	
32		PF05721.15 (Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase (PhyH))	

Table S4.12. antiSMASH annotations of contig Pf7_c00820, detected in GCF 2325 and CC F

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		-	
2		PF13338.8 (Transcriptional regulator, AbiEi antitoxin)	
3	SMCOG1115:HAD-superfamily hydrolase, subfamily IA, variant	PF13419.8 (Haloacid dehalogenase-like hydrolase) TIGR01549 (HAD-SF-IA-v1: HAD hydrolase, family IA, variant 1)	biosynthetic-additional
4		-	
5		PF01850.23 (PIN domain, ribonuclease toxic components of toxin-antitoxin (TA) systems)	
6		-	

7	SMCOG1082:TonB-dependent siderophore receptor family	PF07715.17 (TonB-dependent Receptor Plug Domain) PF00593.26 (TonB dependent receptor)	transport
8	SMCOG1017:aldehyde dehydrogenase	PF00171.24 (Aldehyde dehydrogenase family) PF00171.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00171.24: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
9		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	MiBIG: BGC0000807.1, snas_5663, Stackebrandtia nassauensis, Saccharide, phosphonoglycans
10		PF05721.15 (Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase (PhyH))	
11	SMCOG1288:ABC transporter related protein	PF00664.25 (ABC transporter transmembrane region) PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00664.25: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00664.25: GO:0042626: ATPase-coupled transmembrane transporter activity PF00664.25: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00664.25: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane	Transport MiBIG:BGC0000497.1, bhtT, Streptococcus ratti, RiPP, BHT-A
12		-	
13		PF01850.23 (PIN domain, ribonuclease toxic components of toxin-antitoxin (TA) systems)	
14		PF01011.23 (PQQ enzyme repeat) PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
15		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF06969.18 (HemN C-terminal domain) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional

16		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
17		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
18		PF01011.23 (PQQ enzyme repeat) PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
19	SMCOG1051:TonB-dependent siderophore receptor	PF07715.17 (TonB-dependent Receptor Plug Domain) PF00593.26 (TonB dependent receptor) TIGR01783 (TonB-siderophor: TonB-dependent siderophore receptor)	transport
20		PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG:BGC0000889.1, fevW, Streptomyces sp., Other, bagremycins
21	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG:BGC0001366.1, orf12, Streptomyces sp, Polyketide, zunyimycin A
22		PF11755.10 (Protein of unknown function (DUF3311))	
23		PF00474.19 (Sodium:solute symporter family) PF00474.19: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF00474.19: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00474.19: GO:0016020: membrane	
24	SMCOG1045:glycosyl transferase group 1	PF13439.8 (Glycosyltransferase Family 4) PF00534.22 (Glycosyl transferases group 1) PF00534.22: GO:0016757: transferase activity, transferring glycosyl groups	biosynthetic-additional
25		PF13173.8 (AAA domain) PF13635.8 (Domain of unknown function (DUF4143))	

26		-	
27	SMCOG1014:LysR family transcriptional regulator	PF00126.29 (Bacterial regulatory helix-turn-helix protein, lysR family) PF03466.22 (LysR substrate binding domain) PF00126.29: GO:0003700: DNA-binding transcription factor activity PF00126.29: GO:0006355: regulation of transcription, DNA-templated	regulatory
28	SMCOG1179:hydrolase	PF08282.14 (haloacid dehalogenase-like hydrolase)	biosynthetic-additional

Table S4.13. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM43_c00257, detected in GCF 1884 and CC J

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		-	
2		-	
3	SMCOG1274:gamma-glutamyltranspeptidase	PF01019.23 (Gamma-glutamyltranspeptidase) TIGR00066 (g_glut_trans: gamma-glutamyltransferase)	biosynthetic-additional
4		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
5		PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
6		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
7		-	
8		PF01850.23 (PIN domain)	
9		PF00474.19 (Sodium:solute symporter family)	

		PF00474.19: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF00474.19: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00474.19: GO:0016020: membrane	
10		-	
11		PF12796.9 (Ankyrin repeats (3 copies))	
12		-	
13		-	
14		PF04221.14 (RelB antitoxin) TIGR02384 (RelB_DinJ: addiction module antitoxin, RelB/DinJ family)	
15		PF15738.7 (Bacterial toxin of type II toxin-antitoxin system, YafQ) TIGR02385 (RelE_StbE: addiction module toxin, RelE/StbE family)	
16		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family) TIGR02122 (TRAP_TAXI: TRAP transporter solute receptor, TAXI family)	
17		PF06808.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporter, DctM component) TIGR02123 (TRAP_fused: TRAP transporter, 4TM/12TM fusion protein)	
18		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
19	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG:BGC0001333.1,abeX2, uncultured AB1650, alkaloid BE-54017
20		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	

21	MCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	biosynthetic
22		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
23		-	
24	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding	transport
25		-	
26		PF06182.13 (ABC-2 family transporter protein)	
27		PF06182.13 (ABC-2 family transporter protein)	
28		PF03485.18 (Arginyl tRNA synthetase N terminal domain) PF00750.21 (tRNA synthetases class I (R)) PF05746.17 (DALR anticodon binding domain) PF03485.18: GO:0000166: nucleotide binding PF03485.18: GO:0004814: arginine-tRNA ligase activity PF03485.18: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF03485.18: GO:0006420: arginyl-tRNA aminoacylation PF03485.18: GO:0005737: cytoplasm PF05746.17: GO:0004814: arginine-tRNA ligase activity PF05746.17: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF05746.17: GO:0006420: arginyl-tRNA aminoacylation	
29		PF13669.8 (Glyoxalase/Bleomycin resistance protein/Dioxygenase superfamily) TIGR03081 (metmalonyl_epim: methylmalonyl-CoA epimerase)	
30		PF01048.22 (Phosphorylase superfamily) TIGR01694 (MTAP: methylthioadenosine phosphorylase) PF01048.22: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF01048.22: GO:0009116: nucleoside metabolic process	

31	SMCOG1276:PfkB domain protein	PF00294.26 (pfkB family carbohydrate kinase)	biosynthetic-additional
32		PF01678.21 (Diaminopimelate epimerase) TIGR00652 (DapF: diaminopimelate epimerase) PF01678.21: GO:0008837: diaminopimelate epimerase activity PF01678.21: GO:0009089: lysine biosynthetic process via diaminopimelate	MiBIG:BGC0001733.1, 6800, Pleurocapsa sp., RiPP, PcpA
33		PF01894.19 (Uncharacterised protein family UPF0047) TIGR00149 (TIGR00149_YjbQ: secondary thiamine-phosphate synthase enzyme)	
34	SMCOG1106:major facilitator transporter	PF07690.18 (Major Facilitator Superfamily) PF07690.18: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF07690.18: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport	transport
35		PF02517.18 (Type II CAAX prenyl endopeptidase Rce1-like) PF02517.18: GO:0004222: metalloendopeptidase activity PF02517.18: GO:0071586: CAAX-box protein processing PF02517.18: GO:0016020: membrane	biosynthetic-additional (Abi)
36	SMCOG1220:bifunctional ornithine	PF01960.20 (ArgJ family) TIGR00120 (ArgJ: glutamate N-acetyltransferase/amino-acid acetyltransferase)	biosynthetic-additional
37	SMCOG1063:argininosuccinate lyase/adenylosuccinate lyase	PF00206.22 (Lyase) PF14698.8 (Argininosuccinate lyase C-terminal) TIGR00838 (argH: argininosuccinate lyase)	biosynthetic-additional
38	SMCOG1291:argininosuccinate synthase	PF00764.21 (Arginosuccinate synthase) TIGR00032 (argG: argininosuccinate synthase) PF00764.21: GO:0004055: argininosuccinate synthase activity PF00764.21: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00764.21: GO:0006526: arginine biosynthetic process	biosynthetic-additional

39	SMCOG1114:ornithine carbamoyltransferase	PF02729.23 (Aspartate/ornithine carbamoyltransferase, carbamoyl-P binding domain) PF00185.26 (Aspartate/ornithine carbamoyltransferase, Asp/Orn binding domain) TIGR00658 (orni_carb_tr: ornithine carbamoyltransferase) PF00185.26: GO:0016597: amino acid binding PF00185.26: GO:0016743: carboxyl- or carbamoyltransferase activity PF00185.26: GO:0006520: cellular amino acid metabolic process PF02729.23: GO:0016743: carboxyl- or carbamoyltransferase activity PF02729.23: GO:0006520: cellular amino acid metabolic process	biosynthetic-additional
40	SMCOG1013:aminotransferase class-III	PF00202.23 (Aminotransferase class-III) TIGR00707 (argD: transaminase, acetylornithine/succinylornithine family) PF00202.23: GO:0008483: transaminase activity PF00202.23: GO:0030170: pyridoxal phosphate binding	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG:BGC0000855.1, ectB (L-2,4-diaminobutyric acid acetyl transferase), Methylomicrobium kenyense, Other, ectoine

Table S4.14. antiSMASH annotations of contig gb4_2_c00117, detected in GCF 2554 and CC I

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1	SMCOG1173:WD-40 repeat-containing protein	PF00400.34 (WD domain, G-beta repeat) PF00400.34: GO:0005515: protein binding	
2		-	
3		PF02633.16 (Creatinine amidohydrolase)	
4		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
5		PF01011.23 (PQQ enzyme repeat)	

6		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF06969.18 (HemN C-terminal domain) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
7		PF13360.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
8		PF01344.27 (Kelch motif) TIGR04183 (Por_Secre_tail: Por secretion system C-terminal sorting domain) PF01344.27: GO:0005515: protein binding	
9		PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000889.1, fevW, Streptomyces sp., other, bagremycins
10	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	biosynthetic
11		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family) TIGR02122 (TRAP_TAXI: TRAP transporter solute receptor, TAXI family)	
12		PF06808.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporter, DctM component) TIGR02123 (TRAP_fused: TRAP transporter, 4TM/12TM fusion protein)	
13		PF11755.10 (Protein of unknown function (DUF3311))	
14		PF00474.19 (Sodium:solute symporter family) PF00474.19: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF00474.19: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00474.19: GO:0016020: membrane	
15	SMCOG1045:glycosyl transferase group 1	PF13439.8 (Glycosyltransferase Family 4) PF00534.22 (Glycosyl transferases group 1)	biosynthetic-additional

		PF00534.22: GO:0016757: transferase activity, transferring glycosyl groups	
16		-	
17		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
18	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding	Transport MiBIG: BGC0001526.1,brtl, Synechocystis salina, other, bartolosides
19		PF02687.23 (FtsX-like permease family) PF02687.23: GO:0016020: membrane	
20		PF00892.22 (EamA-like transporter family) PF00892.22: GO:0016020: membrane PF00892.22: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane	
21	SMCOG1122:ATP-dependent RNA helicase	PF00270.31 (DEAD/DEAH box helicase) PF00271.33 (Helicase conserved C-terminal domain) PF09369.12 (Domain of unknown function (DUF1998)) PF00270.31: GO:0003676: nucleic acid binding PF00270.31: GO:0005524: ATP binding	
22	SMCOG1079:oxidoreductase	PF01408.24 (Oxidoreductase family, NAD-binding Rossmann fold) PF02894.19 (Oxidoreductase family, C-terminal alpha/beta domain) PF01408.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity	biosynthetic-additional
23		PF01555.20 (DNA methylase) PF01555.20: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF01555.20: GO:0008170: N-methyltransferase activity PF01555.20: GO:0006306: DNA methylation	
24		PF01555.20 (DNA methylase) PF01555.20: GO:0003677: DNA binding	

		PF01555.20: GO:0008170: N-methyltransferase activity PF01555.20: GO:0006306: DNA methylation	
25		-	

Table S4.15. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM026_c00344, detected in GCF 2138 and CC P

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF02687.23 (FtsX-like permease family) PF12704.9 (MacB-like periplasmic core domain) PF02687.23: GO:0016020: membrane	
2	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding	Transport MiBIG: BGC0000563.1, venT, Streptomyces venezuelae , RiPP, venezuelin
3	SMCOG1112:sigma-54 dependent transcriptional regulator	PF00072.26 (Response regulator receiver domain) PF00158.28 (Sigma-54 interaction domain) PF02954.21 (Bacterial regulatory protein, Fis family) PF00072.26: GO:0000160: phosphorelay signal transduction system PF00158.28: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00158.28: GO:0008134: transcription factor binding PF00158.28: GO:0006355: regulation of transcription, DNA-templated PF02954.21: GO:0043565: sequence-specific DNA binding	Regulatory MiBIG:BGC0001589.1, RS61070, Burkholderia cenocepacia, Saccharide, exopolysaccharides
4	SMCOG1003:sensor histidine kinase	PF02518.28 (Histidine kinase-, DNA gyrase B-, and HSP90-like ATPase)	regulatory
5		PF13202.8 (EF hand) PF13202.8: GO:0005509: calcium ion binding	
6		-	
7		PF02604.21 (Antitoxin Phd_YefM, type II toxin-antitoxin system)	

		TIGR01552 (phd_fam: prevent-host-death family protein)	
8		PF01850.23 (PIN domain, ribonuclease toxic components of toxin-antitoxin (TA) systems)	
9	SMCOG1268:mandelate racemase/muconate lactonizing enzyme	PF02746.18 (Mandelate racemase / muconate lactonizing enzyme, N-terminal domain) PF13378.8 (Enolase C-terminal domain-like)	biosynthetic-additional
10		PF12804.9 (MobA-like NTP transferase domain)	
11		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
12		PF00215.26 (Orotidine 5'-phosphate decarboxylase / HUMPS family) PF00215.26: GO:0004590: orotidine-5'-phosphate decarboxylase activity PF00215.26: GO:0006207: 'de novo' pyrimidine nucleobase biosynthetic process	
13		PF01380.24 (SIS (Sugar Isomerase) domain) PF01380.24: GO:0097367: carbohydrate derivative binding PF01380.24: GO:1901135: carbohydrate derivative metabolic process	
14		PF01850.23 (PIN domain)	
15		PF04014.20 (Antidote-toxin recognition MazE, bacterial antitoxin) PF04014.20: GO:0003677: DNA binding	
16	SMCOG1030:serine/threonine protein kinase	PF00069.27 (Protein kinase domain) PF08308.13 (PEGA domain) PF00069.27: GO:0004672: protein kinase activity PF00069.27: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00069.27: GO:0006468: protein phosphorylation	regulatory

17	SMCOG1255:cold-shock DNA-binding domain protein	PF00313.24 ('Cold-shock' DNA-binding domain) PF00313.24: GO:0003676: nucleic acid binding	regulatory
18		PF13660.8 (Domain of unknown function (DUF4147)) PF05161.15 (MOFRL family)	
19		PF05235.16 (CHAD domain, uncharacterized, metal binding?)	
20		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF06969.18 (HemN C-terminal domain) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
21	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001897.1, 0379, Burkholderia ambifaria, Polyketide, cepacin A
22	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	biosynthetic

Table S4.16. antiSMASH annotations of contig Pf8_c00244, detected in GCF 2270 and CC G

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF12796.9 (Ankyrin repeats (3 copies))	
2	SMCOG1139:aminotransferase class V	PF00266.21 (Aminotransferase class-V)	biosynthetic-additional
3		PF13444.8 (Acetyltransferase (GNAT) domain)	
4		PF14236.8 (Domain of unknown function (DUF4338)) PF14706.8 (Transposase DNA-binding)	
5		PF00872.20 (Transposase, Mutator family)	

		PF00872.20: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF00872.20: GO:0004803: transposase activity PF00872.20: GO:0006313: transposition, DNA-mediated	
6		-	
7		PF13540.8 (Regulator of chromosome condensation (RCC1) repeat)	
8		-	
9		PF13374.8 (Tetratricopeptide repeat)	
10		-	
11		-	
12		PF04290.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporters, DctQ component) TIGR00786 (dctM: TRAP transporter, DctM subunit)	
13		PF03480.15 (Bacterial extracellular solute-binding protein, family 7) PF03480.15: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport	
14		-	
15		-	
16		-	
17		PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
18		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
19		-	

20	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000840.1, AAG38844.2, Xanthomonas oryzae, other, xanthomonadin I, (bmp2)
21	SMCOG1045:glycosyl transferase group 1	PF13439.8 (Glycosyltransferase Family 4) PF00534.22 (Glycosyl transferases group 1) PF00534.22: GO:0016757: transferase activity, transferring glycosyl groups	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000720.1, tbdD, Streptoalloteichus tenebrarius, Saccharide, tobramycin
22		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
23		-	
24	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000466.1, YtkN, Streptomyces sp, NRP, yatakemycin
25		-	
26		-	
27	SMCOG1139:aminotransferase class V	PF00266.21 (Aminotransferase class-V)	biosynthetic-additional
28		-	
29		-	
30		PF19866.1 (Family of unknown function (DUF6339))	
31		PF03235.16 (Protein of unknown function DUF262)	
32		PF00872.20 (Transposase, Mutator family) PF00872.20: GO:0003677: DNA binding	

		PF00872.20: GO:0004803: transposase activity PF00872.20: GO:0006313: transposition, DNA-mediated	
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Table S4.17. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM14B_c00569, detected in GCF 2526 and CC O

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
2	SMCOG1113:inner-membrane translocator	PF02653.18 (Branched-chain amino acid transport system / permease component) PF02653.18: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF02653.18: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF02653.18: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane	transport
3	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding	Transport MiBIG: BGC0000643.1, ABC50111.1, <i>Brevundimonas vesicularis</i> , terpene, carotenoid
4	SMCOG1066:alpha/beta hydrolase domain-containing protein	PF07859.15 (alpha/beta hydrolase fold) PF07859.15: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000820.1, psmB, <i>Streptomyces griseofuscus</i> , alkaloid, physostigmine
5		PF01717.20 (Cobalamin-independent synthase, Catalytic domain) PF01717.20: GO:0003871: 5-methyltetrahydropteroyltriglutamate-homocysteine S-methyltransferase activity PF01717.20: GO:0008270: zinc ion binding PF01717.20: GO:0009086: methionine biosynthetic process	
6		PF01558.20 (Pyruvate ferredoxin/ flavodoxin oxidoreductase) PF01558.20: GO:0016903: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the aldehyde or oxo group of donors PF01558.20: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	

7		PF02775.23 (Thiamine pyrophosphate enzyme, C-terminal TPP binding domain) PF02775.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF02775.23: GO:0030976: thiamine pyrophosphate binding	
8		PF01381.24 (Helix-turn-helix) TIGR02607 (antidote_HigA: addiction module antidote protein, HigA family)	
9		PF05015.15 (RelE-like toxin of type II toxin-antitoxin system HigB)	
10		PF13380.8 (CoA binding domain) PF13607.8 (Succinyl-CoA ligase like flavodoxin domain) PF13549.8 (ATP-grasp domain)	
11		PF06803.14 (Protein of unknown function (DUF1232))	
12		PF02538.16 (Hydantoinase B/oxoprolinase) PF02538.16: GO:0003824: catalytic activity	
13		PF03401.16 (Tripartite tricarboxylate transporter family receptor)	
14		PF13673.9 (Acetyltransferase (GNAT) domain) PF13673.9: GO:0008080: N-acetyltransferase activity	
15		PF03358.17 (NADPH-dependent FMN reductase) PF03358.17: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity	
16	SMCOG1293:aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase	PF01315.24 (Aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase, a/b hammerhead domain) PF02738.20 (Molybdopterin-binding domain of aldehyde dehydrogenase) PF02738.20: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF02738.20: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
17		PF00941.23 (FAD binding domain in molybdopterin dehydrogenase) PF03450.19 (CO dehydrogenase flavoprotein C-terminal domain)	

		PF00941.23: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00941.23: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	
18		PF00111.29 (2Fe-2S iron-sulfur cluster binding domain) PF01799.22 ([2Fe-2S] binding domain) PF00111.29: GO:0009055: electron transfer activity PF00111.29: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding PF01799.22: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF01799.22: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF01799.22: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	MiBIG: BGC0001973.1, Shi4225, Streptomyces hiroshimensis, other, fervenulin
19	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF13193.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000649.1, fadD, Streptomyces griseus, Terpene, carotenoid
20	SMCOG1023:enoyl-CoA hydratase	PF00378.22 (Enoyl-CoA hydratase/isomerase) PF00378.22: GO:0003824: catalytic activity	biosynthetic-additional
21	SMCOG1020:major facilitator transporter	PF05977.15 (Transmembrane secretion effector)	transport
22	SMCOG1050:monooxygenase FAD-binding	PF01494.21 (FAD binding domain) PF01494.21: GO:0071949: FAD binding	biosynthetic
23		PF02776.20 (Thiamine pyrophosphate enzyme, N-terminal TPP binding domain) PF02776.20: GO:0030976: thiamine pyrophosphate binding	
24		PF02775.23 (Thiamine pyrophosphate enzyme, C-terminal TPP binding domain) PF02775.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF02775.23: GO:0030976: thiamine pyrophosphate binding	
25		-	

26		PF01966.24 (HD domain, metal dependent phosphohydrolase)	
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Table S4.18. antiSMASH annotations of contig gb4_2_c02126, detected in GCF 2557 and CC M

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF00939.21 (Sodium:sulfate symporter transmembrane region) TIGR00785 (dass: transporter, divalent anion:Na+ symporter (DASS) family PF00939.21: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF00939.21: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00939.21: GO:0016020: membrane	
2	SMCOG1175:pyridine nucleotide-disulfide oxidoreductase	PF07992.16 (Pyridine nucleotide-disulphide oxidoreductase) PF02852.24 (Pyridine nucleotide-disulphide oxidoreductase, dimerisation domain) TIGR01350 (lipoamide_DH: dihydrolipoyl dehydrogenase)	biosynthetic
3	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme)	biosynthetic
4		-	
5		-	
6	SMCOG1001:short-chain dehydrogenase/reductase SDR	PF13561.8 (Enoyl-(Acyl carrier protein) reductase) 2,3-dihydroxybenzoate-2,3-dehydrogenase	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0001538.1, 23870, Streptomyces sp., NRP, Polyketide, caboxamycin
7		PF05721.15 (Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase (PhyH))	
8		PF00753.29 (Metallo-beta-lactamase superfamily) PF07521.14 (Zn-dependent metallo-hydrolase RNA specificity domain, pre-mRNA 3'-end-processing endonucleases) PF17770.3 (Ribonuclease J C-terminal domain) TIGR00649 (MG423: beta-CASP ribonuclease, RNase J family)	

9		Peptidase_S9	biosynthetic-additional
10	SMCOG1184:major facilitator transporter	PF07690.18 (Major Facilitator Superfamily) PF07690.18: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF07690.18: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport	transport

Table S4.19. antiSMASH annotations of contig gb3_2_c07789, detected in GCF 2484 and CC T

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF08734.13 (GYD domain, unknown function)	
2	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF16177.7 (Acetyl-coenzyme A synthetase N-terminus) PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF13193.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain) TIGR02188 (Ac_CoA_lig_AcsA: acetate--CoA ligase)	biosynthetic
3	SMCOG1161:oxidoreductase	PF05834.14 (Lycopene cyclase protein) TIGR02032 (GG-red-SF: geranylgeranyl reductase family)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000282.1, SGR_470 (monooxygenase), Streptomyces griseus, polyketide, alkylresorcinol
4	SMCOG1146:sugar transferase	PF02397.18 (Bacterial sugar transferase) UDP-glucose dehydrogenase	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0000868.1, tuaA, Bacillus subtilis, other, teichuronic acid
5		PF02673.20 (Bacitracin resistance protein BacA) PF02673.20: GO:0050380: undecaprenyl-diphosphatase activity PF02673.20: GO:0016311: dephosphorylation PF02673.20: GO:0016020: membrane	
6	SMCOG1226:hypothetical protein	PF03781.18 (Sulfatase-modifying factor enzyme 1, domain is also found in iron(II)-dependent oxidoreductase)	

7	SMCOG1268:mandelate racemase/muconate lactonizing enzyme	PF02746.18 (Mandelate racemase / muconate lactonizing enzyme, N-terminal domain, also found in dehydratases) PF13378.8 (Enolase C-terminal domain-like)	biosynthetic-additional
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Table S4.20. antiSMASH annotations of contig DOM057_c01231, detected in GCF 2010 and CC L

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		-	
2	SMCOG1045:glycosyl transferase group 1	PF13439.8 (Glycosyltransferase Family 4) PF00534.22 (Glycosyl transferases group 1) PF00534.22: GO:0016757: transferase activity, transferring glycosyl groups	biosynthetic-additional
3		PF04069.14 (Substrate binding domain of ABC-type glycine betaine transport system) PF04069.14: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF04069.14: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF04069.14: GO:0043190: ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter complex	
4		PF17645.3 (Arylmalonate decarboxylase)	
5		PF01029.20 (NusB family) PF01189.19 (16S rRNA methyltransferase RsmB/F) TIGR00563 (rsmB: 16S rRNA (cytosine(967)-C(5))-methyltransferase) PF01029.20: GO:0003723: RNA binding PF01029.20: GO:0006355: regulation of transcription, DNA-templated PF01189.19: GO:0008168: methyltransferase activity	MiBIG: BGC0002034.1, 28395, Streptomyces sp., other, perquinolines, rRNA cytosine-C5-methyltransferase
6	SMCOG1228:methionyl-tRNA formyltransferase	PF00551.21 (Formyl transferase) PF02911.20 (Formyl transferase, C-terminal domain) TIGR00460 (fmt: methionyl-tRNA formyltransferase) PF00551.21: GO:0016742: hydroxymethyl-, formyl- and related transferase activity PF00551.21: GO:0009058: biosynthetic process	biosynthetic-additional

		PF02911.20: GO:0016742: hydroxymethyl-, formyl- and related transferase activity PF02911.20: GO:0009058: biosynthetic process	
7	SMCOG1275:peptide deformylase	PF01327.23 (Polypeptide deformylase) TIGR00079 (pept_deformyl: peptide deformylase) PF01327.23: GO:0042586: peptide deformylase activity	biosynthetic-additional
8		PF17764.3 (3'DNA-binding domain (3'BD)) PF04851.17 (Type III restriction enzyme, res subunit) PF18319.3 (PriA DNA helicase Cys-rich region (CRR) domain) PF00271.33 (Helicase conserved C-terminal domain) PF18074.3 (Primosomal protein N C-terminal domain) TIGR00595 (priA: primosomal protein N') PF04851.17: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF04851.17: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF04851.17: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity PF17764.3: GO:0003677: DNA binding	
9		PF11104.10 (Type IV pilus assembly protein PilM;) TIGR01175 (pilM: type IV pilus assembly protein PilM)	
10		PF05137.15 (Fimbrial assembly protein (PilN)) PF04350.15 (Pilus assembly protein, PilO) PF04351.15 (Pilus assembly protein, PilP) PF04350.15: GO:0043107: type IV pilus-dependent motility PF04350.15: GO:0043683: type IV pilus biogenesis	
11		-	
12	SMCOG1001:short-chain dehydrogenase/reductase SDR	PF00106.27 (short chain dehydrogenase) PF00106.27: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
13		PF07075.13 (Protein of unknown function (DUF1343))	

14	SMCOG1166:transporter, EamA family	PF00892.22 (EamA-like transporter family) PF00892.22: GO:0016020: membrane PF00892.22: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane	transport
15		PF12838.9 (4Fe-4S dicluster domain, in bacterial ferredoxins, various dehydrogenases, and various reductases)	
16		PF00890.26 (FAD binding domain) PF02910.22 (Fumarate reductase flavoprotein C-term) PF02910.22: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF02910.22: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic
17	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF16177.7 (Acetyl-coenzyme A synthetase N-terminus) PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF13193.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001538.1, 23850, Streptomyces sp., NRP, Polyketide, caboxamycin, Triostin synthetase I
18		PF01977.18 (3-octaprenyl-4-hydroxybenzoate carboxy-lyase) PF01977.18: GO:0016831: carboxy-lyase activity	MiBIG: BGC0000889.1, fevL, Streptomyces sp., other, bagremycin, decarboxylase
19		PF00903.27 (Glyoxalase/Bleomycin resistance protein/Dioxygenase superfamily)	
20		-	
21		PF04909.16 (Amidohydrolase) PF04909.16: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity	
22		PF04909.16 (Amidohydrolase) PF04909.16: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity	
23		DXP_synthase_N (PF13292 - transketolase) PF00676.22 (Dehydrogenase E1 component)	biosynthetic-additional

		PF00676.22: GO:0016624: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the aldehyde or oxo group of donors, disulfide as acceptor	
24	SMCOG1110:1-deoxy-D-xylulose-5-phosphate synthase	PF02779.26 (Transketolase, pyrimidine binding domain) PF02780.22 (Transketolase, C-terminal domain)	biosynthetic-additional
25		PF02633.16 (Creatinine amidohydrolase)	
26		-	
27		-	
28		PF12441.10 (CopG antitoxin of type II toxin-antitoxin system)	
29		-	
30	SMCOG1040:alcohol dehydrogenase	PF08240.14 (Alcohol dehydrogenase GroES-like domain) PF00107.28 (Zinc-binding dehydrogenase) PF00107.28: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF08240.14: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
31		PF07883.13 (Cupin domain)	
32		PF17645.3 (Arylmalonate decarboxylase)	
33		PF03992.18 (Antibiotic biosynthesis monooxygenase)	
34	SMCOG1189:L-carnitine dehydratase/bile acid-inducible	PF02515.19 (CoA-transferase family III) PF02515.19: GO:0008410: CoA-transferase activity	biosynthetic-additional
35		PF05145.14 (Transition state regulatory protein AbrB) PF05145.14: GO:0010468: regulation of gene expression PF05145.14: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane	
36		PF00561 (alpha beta hydrolase fold)	biosynthetic-additional

		Peptidase_S9 PF02129.20 (X-Pro dipeptidyl-peptidase (S15 family)) PF02129.20: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity	
37		-	
38	SMCOG1293:aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase	PF01315.24 (Aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase, a/b hammerhead domain) PF02738.20 (Molybdopterin-binding domain of aldehyde dehydrogenase) PF02738.20: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF02738.20: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
39		-	

Table S4.21. antiSMASH annotations of contig gb4_2_c00127, detected in GCF 2522 and CC N

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		-	
2		PF02604.21 (Antitoxin Phd_YefM, type II toxin-antitoxin system) TIGR01552 (phd_fam: prevent-host-death family protein)	
3		PF01850.23 (PIN domain)	
4		PF01145.27 (SPFH domain / Band 7 family – membrane associated) PF15975.7 (Flotillin)	
5		-	
6		-	
7		PF06808.14 (Tripartite ATP-independent periplasmic transporter, DctM component) TIGR02123 (TRAP_fused: TRAP transporter, 4TM/12TM fusion protein)	
8		PF16868.7 (NMT1-like family)	

		TIGR02122 (TRAP_TAXI: TRAP transporter solute receptor, TAXI family)	
9		PF01661.23 (Macro domain, chromatin biology, DNA repair and transcription regulation)	MiBIG: BGC0000249.1, 42849.1, Streptomyces nogalater, PKS, nogalamycin
10		PF00903.27 (Glyoxalase/Bleomycin resistance protein/Dioxygenase superfamily)	
11		PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF14535.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000889.1, fevW, Streptomyces sp., other, bagremycin
12		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
13	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001366.1, orf12, Streptomyces sp, PKS, zunyimycin, Trp_halogenase
14		-	
15		PF04055.23 (Radical SAM superfamily) PF04055.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity PF04055.23: GO:0051536: iron-sulfur cluster binding	biosynthetic-additional
16		PF13570.8 (PQQ-like domain)	
17		PF00465.21 (Iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase) PF00465.21: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00465.21: GO:0046872: metal ion binding PF00465.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction proces	
18		PF02518.28 (Histidine kinase-, DNA gyrase B-, and HSP90-like ATPase) PF00204.27 (DNA gyrase B)	MiBIG:

		<p>PF01751.24 (Toprim domain) PF00986.23 (DNA gyrase B subunit, carboxyl terminus) PF00204.27: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF00204.27: GO:0003918: DNA topoisomerase type II (double strand cut, ATP-hydrolyzing) activity PF00204.27: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00204.27: GO:0006265: DNA topological change PF00986.23: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF00986.23: GO:0003918: DNA topoisomerase type II (double strand cut, ATP-hydrolyzing) activity PF00986.23: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00986.23: GO:0006265: DNA topological change</p>	
19		<p>PF00521.22 (DNA gyrase/topoisomerase IV, subunit A) PF00521.22: GO:0003677: DNA binding PF00521.22: GO:0003918: DNA topoisomerase type II (double strand cut, ATP-hydrolyzing) activity PF00521.22: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF00521.22: GO:0006265: DNA topological change</p>	
20		<p>PF00293.30 (NUDIX domain, pyrophosphohydrolases) PF00293.30: GO:0016787: hydrolase activity</p>	
21	SMCOG1086:MATE efflux family protein	<p>PF01554.20 (MatE) TIGR00797 (matE: MATE efflux family protein) PF01554.20: GO:0015297: antiporter activity PF01554.20: GO:0042910: xenobiotic transmembrane transporter activity PF01554.20: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF01554.20: GO:0016020: membrane</p>	transport
22	SMCOG1168:O-succinylhomoserine sulfhydrylase	<p>PF01053.22 (Cys/Met metabolism PLP-dependent enzyme) PF01053.22: GO:0030170: pyridoxal phosphate binding PF01053.22: GO:0019346: transsulfuration</p>	biosynthetic-additional

23		PF00583.27 (Acetyltransferase (GNAT) family) PF00583.27: GO:0008080: N-acetyltransferase activity	
24	SMCOG1040:alcohol dehydrogenase	PF08240.14 (Alcohol dehydrogenase GroES-like domain) PF00107.28 (Zinc-binding dehydrogenase) PF00107.28: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF08240.14: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
25		-	
26	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00550.27 (Phosphopantetheine attachment site) PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF01553.23 (Acyltransferase) PF01553.23: GO:0016746: transferase activity, transferring acyl groups	biosynthetic
27		PF00160.23 (Cyclophilin type peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase/CLD) PF00160.23: GO:0003755: peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase activity PF00160.23: GO:0000413: protein peptidyl-prolyl isomerization	
28		PF00160.23 (Cyclophilin type peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase/CLD) PF00160.23: GO:0003755: peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase activity PF00160.23: GO:0000413: protein peptidyl-prolyl isomerization	
29		-	

Table S4.22. antiSMASH annotations of contig gb9_c09452, detected in GCF 2609 and CC Q

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		PF12697.9 (Alpha/beta hydrolase family)	biosynthetic-additional
2	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF13193.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000649.1, fadD, Streptomyces griseus, terpene, carotenoid

3	SMCOG1119:halogenase	PF04820.16 (Tryptophan halogenase)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0000840.1, 38844.2, Xanthomonas oryzae, other, xanthomonadin
4		- (blast – putative ACP)	
5	SMCOG1001:short-chain dehydrogenase/reductase SDR	PF13561.8 (Enoyl-(Acyl carrier protein) reductase)	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0001987.1, 02930, Pseudomonas koreensis, PKS, koreenceines, 3-oxoacyl-ACP reductase
6		PF00916.22 (Sulfate permease family) PF00916.22: GO:0015116: sulfate transmembrane transporter activity PF00916.22: GO:0008272: sulfate transport PF00916.22: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane	

Table S4.23. antiSMASH annotations of contig Pf7_c00139, detected in GCF 2366 and CC S

Gene	SMCOG	PFAM & GO	Notes
1		-	
2	SMCOG1207:inositol monophosphatase	PF00459.27 (Inositol monophosphatase family) PF00459.27: GO:0046855: inositol phosphate dephosphorylation	biosynthetic-additional
3		PF01222.19 (Ergosterol biosynthesis ERG4/ERG24 family) PF01222.19: GO:0016628: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors, NAD or NADP as acceptor PF01222.19: GO:0016126: sterol biosynthetic process PF01222.19: GO:0016020: membrane	
4		PF01222.19 (Ergosterol biosynthesis ERG4/ERG24 family)	

		PF01222.19: GO:0016628: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors, NAD or NADP as acceptor PF01222.19: GO:0016126: sterol biosynthetic process PF01222.19: GO:0016020: membrane	
5		-	
6		-	
7		PF03061.24 (Thioesterase superfamily)	
8		PF08768.13 (THAP4-like, heme-binding beta-barrel domain), putatively related to fatty acid-binding proteins	
9	SMCOG1092:hypothetical protein	PF13450.8 (NAD(P)-binding Rossmann-like domain)	
10		PF01212.23 (Beta-eliminating lyase) PF01212.23: GO:0016829: lyase activity PF01212.23: GO:0006520: cellular amino acid metabolic process (PF01041: pyridoxal-phosphate-dependent aminotransferase enzymes with a variety of molecular functions)	biosynthetic-additional DegT_DnrJ_EryC1
11		PF07969.13 (Amidohydrolase family)	
12		-	
13	SMCOG1160:flavin reductase domain protein FMN-binding	PF01613.20 (Flavin reductase like domain) PF01613.20: GO:0010181: FMN binding	biosynthetic-additional
14		PF01176.21 (Translation initiation factor 1A / IF-1) TIGR00008 (infA: translation initiation factor IF-1) PF01176.21: GO:0003723: RNA binding PF01176.21: GO:0003743: translation initiation factor activity PF01176.21: GO:0006413: translational initiation	

15	SMCOG1023:enoyl-CoA hydratase	PF00378.22 (Enoyl-CoA hydratase/isomerase) PF00378.22: GO:0003824: catalytic activity	biosynthetic-additional
16	SMCOG1006:acyl-CoA dehydrogenase	PF02771.18 (Acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, N-terminal domain) PF02770.21 (Acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, middle domain) PF00441.26 (Acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, C-terminal domain) PF00441.26: GO:0016627: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors PF00441.26: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF02770.21: GO:0016627: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors PF02770.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF02771.18: GO:0016627: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors PF02771.18: GO:0050660: flavin adenine dinucleotide binding PF02771.18: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional
17		PF13416.8 (Bacterial extracellular solute-binding protein):	
18	SMCOG1069:putative ABC transporter permease protein	PF00528.24 (Binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component) PF00528.24: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00528.24: GO:0016020: membrane	transport
19	SMCOG1069:putative ABC transporter permease protein	PF00528.24 (Binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component) PF00528.24: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF00528.24: GO:0016020: membrane	transport
20	SMCOG1000:ABC transporter ATP-binding protein	PF00005.29 (ABC transporter) PF08402.12 (TOBE domain) TIGR01187 (potA: polyamine ABC transporter, ATP-binding protein) PF00005.29: GO:0005524: ATP binding PF08402.12: GO:0005524: ATP binding	transport

		PF08402.12: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF08402.12: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF08402.12: GO:0043190: ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter complex	
21		PF00491.23 (Arginase family) TIGR01230 (agmatinase: agmatinase) PF00491.23: GO:0046872: metal ion binding	
22		-	
23	SMCOG1103:FAD dependent oxidoreductase	PF01266.26 (FAD dependent oxidoreductase) PF01266.26: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF01266.26: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic
24		PF00753.29 (Metallo-beta-lactamase superfamily)	
25		PF11716.10 (Mycothioli maleylpyruvate isomerase metal-binding N-terminal domain) TIGR03086 (TIGR03086: TIGR03086 family protein) TIGR03083 (TIGR03083: uncharacterized Actinobacterial protein TIGR03083) PF11716.10: GO:0046872: metal ion binding	
26		-	
27		PF03631.17 (Virulence factor BrkB)	
28	SMCOG1002:AMP-dependent synthetase and ligase	PF00501.30 (AMP-binding enzyme) PF13193.8 (AMP-binding enzyme C-terminal domain)	Biosynthetic MiBIG: BGC0001538.1, 23850, Streptomyces sp., NRP, Polyketide, caboxamycin
29	SMCOG1134:flavodoxin	PF04879.18 (Molybdopterin oxidoreductase Fe4S4 domain) PF00384.24 (Molybdopterin oxidoreductase) PF01568.23 (Molybdopterin dinucleotide binding domain) PF00384.24: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF00384.24: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0001441.1, belN, Streptomyces sp., other, belactosin

		<p>PF01568.23: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF01568.23: GO:0043546: molybdopterin cofactor binding PF01568.23: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process PF04879.18: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity PF04879.18: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p>	
30	SMCOG1202:major facilitator transportee	<p>PF07690.18 (Major Facilitator Superfamily) PF07690.18: GO:0022857: transmembrane transporter activity PF07690.18: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport</p>	transport
31		<p>PF01699.26 (Sodium/calcium exchanger protein) TIGR00367 (TIGR00367: K+-dependent Na+/Ca+ exchanger homolog) PF01699.26: GO:0055085: transmembrane transport PF01699.26: GO:0016021: integral component of membrane</p>	
32		<p>PF00920.23 (Dehydratase family) PF00920.23: GO:0003824: catalytic activity</p>	
33		<p>PF00676.22 (pyruvate Dehydrogenase E1 component, acetyl transferring) PF00676.22: GO:0016624: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the aldehyde or oxo group of donors, disulfide as acceptor</p>	MiBIG: BGC0001535.1, bkdA1, Streptomyces filamentosus, other, daptomycin analogs
34	SMCOG1110:1-deoxy-D-xylulose-5-phosphate synthase	<p>PF02779.26 (Transketolase, pyrimidine binding domain) PF02780.22 (Transketolase, C-terminal domain)</p>	biosynthetic-additional MiBIG: BGC0001535.1, bkdB1, Streptomyces filamentosus, other, daptomycin analogs
35		<p>PF01513.23 (ATP-NAD kinase N-terminal domain) PF01513.23: GO:0003951: NAD+ kinase activity PF01513.23: GO:0006741: NADP biosynthetic process</p>	
36		<p>PF00364.24 (Biotin-requiring enzyme) PF02817.19 (e3 binding domain) PF00198.25 (2-oxoacid dehydrogenases acyltransferase (catalytic domain)) PF00198.25: GO:0016746: transferase activity, transferring acyl groups</p>	MiBIG: BGC0001535.1, bkdC2, Streptomyces filamentosus, other, daptomycin analogs

		PF02817.19: GO:0016746: transferase activity, transferring acyl groups	
37	SMCOG1006:acyl-CoA dehydrogenase	<p>PF02771.18 (Acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, N-terminal domain)</p> <p>PF02770.21 (Acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, middle domain)</p> <p>PF00441.26 (Acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, C-terminal domain)</p> <p>PF00441.26: GO:0016627: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors</p> <p>PF00441.26: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p> <p>PF02770.21: GO:0016627: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors</p> <p>PF02770.21: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p> <p>PF02771.18: GO:0016627: oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors</p> <p>PF02771.18: GO:0050660: flavin adenine dinucleotide binding</p> <p>PF02771.18: GO:0055114: oxidation-reduction process</p>	<p>biosynthetic-additional</p> <p>MiBIG: BGC0000886.1, allD, Streptomyces tsukubensis, other, allylmalonyl-CoA</p>
38		PF00903.27 (Glyoxalase/Bleomycin resistance protein/Dioxygenase superfamily)	
39	SMCOG1092:hypothetical protein	PF13450.8 (NAD(P)-binding Rossmann-like domain)	<p>MiBIG: BGC0001625.1, ifqQ, Streptomyces sp., other, isofuranonaphthoquinone, Baeyer-Villiger monooxygenase</p>
40		<p>PF12710.9 (haloacid dehalogenase-like hydrolase)</p> <p>TIGR02137 (HSK-PSP: phosphoserine phosphatase/homoserine phosphotransferase bifunctional protein)</p>	
41		<p>PF08534.12 (Redoxin)</p> <p>PF08534.12: GO:0016491: oxidoreductase activity</p>	
42	SMCOG1108:ROK family protein	PF00480.22 (ROK (Repressor, ORF, Kinase) family)	

43	PF02113.17 (D-Ala-D-Ala carboxypeptidase 3 (S13) family) TIGR00666 (PBP4: D-alanyl-D-alanine carboxypeptidase/D-alanyl-D-alanine-endopeptidase) PF02113.17: GO:0004185: serine-type carboxypeptidase activity PF02113.17: GO:0006508: proteolysis
44	PF02190.18 (ATP-dependent protease La (LON) substrate-binding domain)

Table S5. Description of regulator elements as detected by antiSMASH 7 (beta) on CC representative contigs.

Contig	GCF	CC	Regulator	Location	Description	Score
Pf12_c00118	2286	A	AfsR	5,401	Pleiotropic regulatory for antibiotic production	18.46 out of 23.05
Pf12_c00118	2286	A	AbrC3	29,809	Antibiotic production activator	18.07 out of 18.16
gb5_2_c00041	2402	E	AbrC3	11,303	Antibiotic production activator	17.35 out of 18.16
gb5_2_c00041	2402	E	CatR	15,415	H2O2-responsive repressor	20.57 out of 25.31
Pf12_c00284	2043	K	ZuR	32,803	Zinc-responsive repressor	20.85 out of 28.19
Pf11_c00818	2559	H	NrdR	12,295	Represses ribonucleotide reductase encoding genes	23.69 out of 27.18
Pf11_c00818	2559	H	LexA	18,416	Repressor of DNA damage response	23.92 out of 29.65
DOM044_c00402	1983	D	AbrC3	32,418	Antibiotic production activator	18.07 out of 18.16
DOM044_c00402	1983	D	ZuR	32,531	Zinc-responsive repressor	21.63 out of 28.19
DOM14B_c00569	2526	O	CatR	14,503	H2O2-responsive repressor	21.85 out of 25.31
gb9_c09452	2609	Q	BldD	1,031	Development and antibiotic global regulator	20.01 out of 23.43

Table S6. CC A A-domain AdenylPred functional class and substrate specificity predictions.

A-domain	Predicted functional class (FC)	FC prediction probability	Predicted substrate specificity (SS)	SS prediction probability
Pf6_c44645_NODE_44...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_304_1795	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
gb9_c07451_NODE_74...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_5_6089_7670	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
DOM049_bin.11.strict_NODE_225_length_5496_cov_4.16 1100.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_3_2962_4495	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27

gb10_c02489_NODE_24...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_0_1551	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
DOM044_c02058_NODE_20...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_9_6580_8362	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
gb5_2_c09272_NODE_92...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_5_6167_7748	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
DOM43_c00933_NODE_93...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_17_17919_19428	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.43	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
Pf11_c16311_NODE_16...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_0_1470	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Pf4_c01746_NODE_17...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_344_1835	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Pf7_c22554_NODE_22...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_87_1578	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Aply22_bin.20.strict_NODE_213_length_4775_cov_6.472669.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_4_3197_4688	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Pf8_c16919_NODE_16...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_3_2598_4089	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Pf12_bin.52.strict_NODE_4_length_127629_cov_21.520321.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_17_16001_17492	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Aply23_bin.9.strict_NODE_85_length_10472_cov_3.930498.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_4_2789_4280	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Pf10_c10573_NODE_10...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_85_1576	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
DOM011_c01245_NODE_12...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_14_16222_17731	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
Pf11_c00891_NODE_89...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_25_20000_21491	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.46	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.28
Pf9_c05741_NODE_57...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_11_9051_9366	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.56	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.35
Pf5_c01370_NODE_13...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_16_16011_17502	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24

Pf9_c28236_NODE_28...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_2_557_2048	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Aply21_c08313_NODE_83...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_4_2959_3403	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.55	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.32
DOM33_c00105_NODE_10...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_2_1113_2622	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
DOM14B_c25243_NODE_25...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_57_1575	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
DOM026_c12884_NODE_12...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_5_2363_3872	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.41	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.24
Pf5_bin.39.strict_NODE_3_length_52011_cov_5.124158.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_3_2028_3519	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.46	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.28
gb1_bin.48.strict_NODE_59_length_14622_cov_7.645239.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_13_13050_14622	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
DOM045_bin.2.strict_NODE_2_length_313427_cov_20.378002.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_11_10546_12055	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
Aply16_c09216_NODE_92...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_4_2977_3976	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.5	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.26
gb4_2_bin.24.strict_NODE_46_length_17554_cov_6.212451.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_12_12732_14685	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
gb2_2_bin.25.strict_NODE_63_length_13684_cov_7.323436.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_12_12703_13684	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.5	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.3
DOM43_bin.27.strict_NODE_22_length_35237_cov_8.092804.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_2_642_2151	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.43	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27
gb6_bin.52.strict_NODE_30_length_20515_cov_7.543987.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_17_19651_20515	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.32	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.13
gb8_2_c49583_NODE_49...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_2_1257_2838	Aryl-CoA ligase	0.42	cinnamate and succinylbenzoate derivatives	0.27

Table S7. PARAS extracted and aligned Stachelhaus and extended active site residues of A-domains in CC A, Genieus alignment statistics and WebLogos.

A-domain	DomainStachelhaus	Active Site
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Aply16_c09216_NODE_92...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_4_2977_3976	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Aply21_c08313_NODE_83...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_4_2959_3403	---YLV-VR	-----AYALVVDE----GRIGTEVRSVA
Aply22_bin.20.strict_NODE_213_length_4775_cov_6.472669.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_4_3197_4688	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Aply23_bin.9.strict_NODE_85_length_10472_cov_3.930498.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_4_2789_4280	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM011_c01245_NODE_12...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_14_16222_17731	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM026_c12884_NODE_12...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_5_2363_3872	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM044_c02058_NODE_20...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_9_6580_8362	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM045_bin.2.strict_NODE_2_length_313427_cov_20.378002.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_11_10546_12055	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM049_bin.11.strict_NODE_225_length_5496_cov_4.161100.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_3_2962_4495	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM14B_c25243_NODE_25...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_57_1575	AVMFGGHPL	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM33_c00105_NODE_10...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_2_1113_2622	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM43_bin.27.strict_NODE_22_length_35237_cov_8.092804.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_2_642_2151	AVMFGGHPL	STTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
DOM43_c00933_NODE_93...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_17_17919_19428	AVMFGGHPL	STTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf10_c10573_NODE_10...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_85_1576	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf11_c00891_NODE_89...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_25_20000_21491	AVMFGGHPL	STTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf11_c16311_NODE_16...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_0_1470	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf12_bin.52.strict_NODE_4_length_127629_cov_21.520321.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_17_16001_17492	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf4_c01746_NODE_17...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_344_1835	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf5_bin.39.strict_NODE_3_length_52011_cov_5.124158.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_3_2028_3519	AVMFGGHPL	STTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf5_c01370_NODE_13...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_16_16011_17502	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf6_c44645_NODE_44...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_304_1795	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf7_c22554_NODE_22...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_87_1578	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
Pf8_c16919_NODE_16...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_3_2598_4089	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL

Pf9_c05741_NODE_57...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_11_9051_9366	---L-----	-----GLY-----
Pf9_c28236_NODE_28...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_2_557_2048	AVMFGGHPL	SSTVHAVGLMIQFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
gb10_c02489_NODE_24...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_1_0_1551	AVMFGGHPL	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
gb1_bin.48.strict_NODE_59_length_14622_cov_7.645239.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_13_13050_14622	AVMFGGHPL	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
gb2_2_bin.25.strict_NODE_63_length_13684_cov_7.323436.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_12_12703_13684	AVMFGGH--	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSET-----
gb4_2_bin.24.strict_NODE_46_length_17554_cov_6.212451.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_12_12732_14685	AVMFGGHPL	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
gb5_2_c09272_NODE_92...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_5_6167_7748	AVMFGGHPL	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
gb6_bin.52.strict_NODE_30_length_20515_cov_7.543987.region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_17_19651_20515	AVMFGG---	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGA-----
gb8_2_c49583_NODE_49...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_2_1257_2838	AVMFGGHPL	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
gb9_c07451_NODE_74...region001_haloAMP_AMP-binding_5_6089_7670	AVMFGGHPL	SSTTHAVGLMIAFLGVGGATDHYGQSETGPLTIL
PARAS active site statistics (ungapped only):		
Length (mean): 34 aa (34 codons)		
Sequences: 29		
Identical Sites: 31 (91.2%)		
Pairwise Identity: 96.4%		
Pairwise Positive (BLSM62): 97.1%		
Stachelhaus residues statistics (ungapped only):		
Length (mean): 9 aa (9 codons)		
Sequences: 29		
Identical Sites: 9 (100.0%)		

Table S8. Acidobacteria Bin61 MAG information.

Genome	Completeness	Contamination	Strain heterogeneity	Length	N50	Taxonomic classification
Aply22_bin.20.strict.fa	87.29	0.96	33.33	344186 6	17362	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__Bin61 sp002238705
Aply23_bin.9.strict.fa	71.12	1.29	0.0	301952 8	9569	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__Bin61 sp002238705
DOM007A_bin.35.strict.fa	88.84	0.85	0.0	270539 3	1384733	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM007B_bin.2.strict.fa	88.84	0.85	0.0	276617 9	486662	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM011_bin.33.orig.fa	92.68	0.85	0.0	441037 9	48964	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM012A_bin.31.strict.fa	83.56	1.78	0.0	296363 2	16420	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM013_bin.40.orig.fa	80.17	1.78	33.33	253733 6	8169	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM015_bin.63.strict.fa	85.09	2.14	0.0	263133 8	12893	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM016_bin.38.permissive.fa	87.98	0.9	0.0	270875 5	492822	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM026_bin.53.orig.fa	82.05	0.85	0.0	291855 2	14826	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__

DOM044_bin.47.orig.fa	92.74	2.56	25.0	4505327	47868	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM045_bin.2.strict.fa	91.88	2.19	0.0	4273376	120250	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM049_bin.11.strict.fa	83.01	0.85	0.0	3504759	14813	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM057_bin.38.orig.fa	85.42	0.85	0.0	2642392	322731	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM10_bin.63.orig.fa	86.75	0.0	0.0	3532383	141441	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM14B_bin.52.orig.fa	90.12	0.85	0.0	4101197	26286	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM33_bin.71.orig.fa	91.88	0.85	0.0	4124016	167581	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM40_bin.43.strict.fa	89.79	0.85	0.0	3487366	40484	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
DOM43_bin.14.orig.fa	59.07	5.23	11.11	3539402	2915	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__SMYC01;g__s__
DOM43_bin.27.strict.fa	87.87	3.42	20.0	3216245	27215	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb1_bin.48.strict.fa	87.18	0.91	0.0	3121056	12235	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb10_bin.24.orig.fa	72.81	0.0	0.0	2826534	5528	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb126_bin.28.strict.fa	83.05	6.03	0.0	3987243	9045	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__SMYC01;g__SMYC01;s__
gb126_bin.4.strict.fa	54.74	0.0	0.0	2194644	4614	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb126_bin.57.orig.fa	50.68	4.13	50.0	3028711	2666	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__SMYC01;g__s__
gb2_2_bin.25.strict.fa	83.12	0.85	0.0	3072413	12488	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__

gb278_bin.12.strict.fa	58.95	7.26	0.0	2733024	2974	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__SMYC01;g__s__
gb278_bin.29.strict.fa	65.93	2.14	62.5	3443931	6145	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__SMYC01;g__SMYC01;s__
gb278_bin.7.strict.fa	73.36	0.11	0.0	2574323	5603	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb3_2_bin.12.strict.fa	82.48	0.85	0.0	3020087	12511	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb305_bin.4.strict.fa	81.31	6.93	0.0	5007556	9998	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__SMYC01;g__SMYC01;s__
gb305_bin.59.strict.fa	73.65	0.85	0.0	2407354	6046	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb4_2_bin.24.strict.fa	83.45	1.71	0.0	3165550	13053	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb5_2_bin.40.orig.fa	82.48	0.85	0.0	2884449	5273	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb6_bin.52.strict.fa	88.68	0.91	0.0	3095017	12948	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb7_bin.26.strict.fa	81.41	0.85	0.0	2910222	8040	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb8_2_bin.28.orig.fa	72.98	0.0	0.0	2901044	5907	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
gb9_bin.7.orig.fa	83.76	0.85	0.0	2845379	6180	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf10_bin.25.orig.fa	87.98	0.85	0.0	3227732	15336	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf11_bin.29.orig.fa	66.67	0.0	0.0	2216665	42881	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf11_bin.41.strict.fa	52.63	1.75	100.0	1829438	9676	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf12_bin.52.strict.fa	91.4	0.9	0.0	3790910	65216	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__

Pf4_bin.17.orig.fa	91.83	0.85	0.0	3822207	42050	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf5_bin.12.strict.fa	91.4	0.85	0.0	3720584	55861	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__Bin61 sp002238705
Pf5_bin.39.strict.fa	90.64	2.02	20.0	2993178	21997	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf6_bin.12.orig.fa	87.13	0.85	0.0	3112957	12796	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf8_bin.35.orig.fa	88.84	0.85	0.0	3370558	14062	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf9_bin.26.orig.fa	82.0	1.71	20.0	2994752	21154	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__
Pf9_bin.51.orig.fa	74.07	1.85	20.0	2429284	5242	d__Bacteria;p__Acidobacteriota;c__Bin61;o__Bin61;f__Bin61;g__Bin61;s__

Table S9. CC A and SwissProt single domain P450 CYP/KO annotation.

P450	KO	e-value	bitscore	CYP	e-value2	bitscore3
gb9_c07451_NODE_74...region001_haloAMP_p450_1_184_1519	K21164	1.1e-127	427.2	CYP253A1	5.27e-91	282
gb9_c07451_NODE_74...region001_haloAMP_p450_2_1772_3116	K21164	1.9e-110	370.5	CYP253B2	1.13e-86	271
gb10_c02489_NODE_24...region001_haloAMP_p450_4_4524_5868	K21164	6.6e-111	372.0	CYP253B2	7.90e-86	270
gb10_c02489_NODE_24...region001_haloAMP_p450_5_6121_7456	K21164	1.1e-127	427.2	CYP253A1	5.27e-91	282
gb10_c02489_NODE_24...region001_haloAMP_p450_6_7699_8968	K21164	3.9e-107	359.6	CYP253A1	6.08e-76	243
DOM044_c02058_NODE_20...region001_haloAMP_p450_13_11922_13269	K21164	9.9e-127	424.2	CYP253B2	4.53e-95	293
gb5_2_c09272_NODE_92...region001_haloAMP_p450_1_262_1597	K21164	1.1e-127	427.2	CYP253A1	5.27e-91	282

gb5_2_c09272_NODE_92...region001_haloAMP_p450_2_1850_3194	K21164	7.2e-112	375.2	CYP253B2	1.42e-85	269
DOM43_c00933_NODE_93...region001_haloAMP_p450_19_22387_23731	K21164	1.1e-123	414.1	CYP253B1	7.35e-90	280
Pf4_c01746_NODE_17...region001_haloAMP_p450_4_4545_5895	K21164	1.1e-126	424.0	CYP197A1	1.03e-96	296
Aply22_bin.20.strict_NODE_213_length_4775_cov_6.472669.region001_haloAMP_p450_1_2_482	K21164	1.6e-56	192.8	CYP253C1	9.62e-45	150
Pf12_bin.52.strict_NODE_4_length_127629_cov_21.520321.region001_haloAMP_p450_14_11936_13286	K21164	3.2e-126	422.5	CYP197A1	2.10e-96	296
Pf10_c10573_NODE_10...region001_haloAMP_p450_4_4291_5641	K21164	9,00E-127	424.3	CYP197A1	1.32e-96	296
DOM011_c01245_NODE_12...region001_haloAMP_p450_17_20451_21801	K21164	1.7e-126	423.4	CYP197A1	6.16e-94	289
Pf11_c00891_NODE_89...region001_haloAMP_p450_28_24188_25535	K21164	5.2e-125	418.5	CYP253B2	1.22e-92	287
Pf9_c05741_NODE_57...region001_haloAMP_p450_8_5005_6352	K21164	1.7e-123	413.5	CYP253B2	7.12e-95	293
Pf5_c01370_NODE_13...region001_haloAMP_p450_13_11947_13297	K21164	9,00E-127	424.3	CYP197A1	1.32e-96	296
Aply21_c08313_NODE_83...region001_haloAMP_p450_1_1_244	K15001	4.2e-23	82.1	CYP262A1	6.05e-21	83.2
DOM33_c00105_NODE_10...region001_haloAMP_p450_5_5344_6694	K21164	2.5e-126	422.8	CYP253B2	1.69e-95	295
DOM14B_c25243_NODE_25...region001_haloAMP_p450_4_4321_5671	K21164	2,00E-125	419.9	CYP253A2	1.46e-93	288
gb1_bin.48.strict_NODE_59_length_14622_cov_7.645239.region001_haloAMP_p450_8_5644_6913	K21164	5.8e-107	359.0	CYP253A1	6.08e-76	243
gb1_bin.48.strict_NODE_59_length_14622_cov_7.645239.region001_haloAMP_p450_9_7157_8492	K21164	1.1e-127	427.2	CYP253A1	5.27e-91	282
gb1_bin.48.strict_NODE_59_length_14622_cov_7.645239.region001_haloAMP_p450_10_8745_10089	K21164	2.1e-111	373.7	CYP253B2	2.28e-86	271

DOM045_bin.2.strict_NODE_2_length_313427_cov_2 0.378002.region001_haloAMP_p450_7_5633_6983	K21164	5.9e-126	421.6	CYP253B2	5.78e-94	290
Aply16_c09216_NODE_92...region001_haloAMP_p450_1_2_263	K15001	6.6e-28	98.0	CYP253C1	1.33e-22	88.2
gb4_2_bin.24.strict_NODE_46_length_17554_cov_6.2 12451.region001_haloAMP_p450_7_5314_6583	K21164	3.9e-107	359.6	CYP253A1	6.08e-76	243
gb4_2_bin.24.strict_NODE_46_length_17554_cov_6.2 12451.region001_haloAMP_p450_8_6827_8162	K21164	1.1e-127	427.2	CYP253A1	5.27e-91	282
gb4_2_bin.24.strict_NODE_46_length_17554_cov_6.2 12451.region001_haloAMP_p450_9_8415_9759	K21164	2.5e-111	373.4	CYP253B2	2.07e-86	271
gb2_2_bin.25.strict_NODE_63_length_13684_cov_7.3 23436.region001_haloAMP_p450_7_5285_6554	K21164	3.9e-107	359.6	CYP253A1	6.08e-76	243
gb2_2_bin.25.strict_NODE_63_length_13684_cov_7.3 23436.region001_haloAMP_p450_8_6798_8133	K21164	1.1e-127	427.2	CYP253A1	5.27e-91	282
gb2_2_bin.25.strict_NODE_63_length_13684_cov_7.3 23436.region001_haloAMP_p450_9_8386_9730	K21164	1.9e-110	370.5	CYP253B2	1.13e-86	271
DOM43_bin.27.strict_NODE_22_length_35237_cov_8. 092804.region001_haloAMP_p450_5_4872_6216	K21164	5.5e-123	411.8	CYP253B1	2.26e-90	281
gb6_bin.52.strict_NODE_30_length_20515_cov_7.543 987.region001_haloAMP_p450_12_12245_13514	K21164	3.9e-107	359.6	CYP253A1	6.08e-76	243
gb6_bin.52.strict_NODE_30_length_20515_cov_7.543 987.region001_haloAMP_p450_13_13758_15093	K21164	1.1e-127	427.2	CYP253A1	5.27e-91	282
gb6_bin.52.strict_NODE_30_length_20515_cov_7.543 987.region001_haloAMP_p450_14_15346_16690	K21164	1.9e-110	370.5	CYP253B2	1.13e-86	271
DOM015_c02570_NODE_25...region001_haloAMP_p450_2_266_1178	K21164	1.5e-28	100.6	CYP286A1	1.95e-43	152
DOM044_c01110_NODE_11...region001_haloAMP_p450_22_13908_15156	K16593	1.6e-127	426.3	CYP107AZ1	1.34e-113	337
DOM33_c01507_NODE_15...region001_haloAMP_p450_21_26204_27473	K16593	2.4e-108	363.2	CYP1011B1	1.11e-103	312
DOM33_c01988_NODE_19...region001_haloAMP_p450_23_19387_20641	K16593	5.6e-127	424.5	CYP107AZ1	7.73e-115	340

PLPH_bmp7_AHA34040.1_BGC0000890	K17814	7.2e-102	342.2	Cyp2r1	2.06e-59	202
PL2TA16_bmp7_ESP90850.1_BGC0000891	K17814	3.9e-98	329.9	CYP1A1	9.37e-59	201
MARME_bmp7_WP_013663197.1_BGC0001465	K17814	1.9e-92	311.1	CYP1A1	1.37e-56	195
GUM202_bmp7_MBO1347623.1	K23139	2.9e-180	600.1	CYP110C6	0.0	514
GUM202_bmp12_MBO1347626.1	K17814	4.3e-120	402.3	CYP1C2	2.43e-71	234
sp AOR4Q6 CP142_MYCS2	K16046	3.3e-216	718.0	CYP142A2	0.0	819
sp AOR4Y3 CP125_MYCS2	K15981	2.4e-212	705.4	CYP125A3	0.0	883
sp A4F7P2 ERYC2_SACEN	K15997	7.4e-228	756.0	CYP131A1	2.49e-24	102
sp B4XY99 AZIB1_STREG	K21376	4.4e-291	964.7	CYP1019A1	1.23e-49	171
sp C4B644 CPVDH_PSEAH	K24389	3.7e-240	796.9	CYP107BR1	0.0	808
sp C9K1X6 COTB3_STRMJ	K22997	9,00E-249	826.1	CYP183B1	2.90e-129	380
sp C9K1X7 COTB4_STRMJ	K22998	0	1016.7	CYP183A2	5.24e-133	389
sp D5E3H2 CP107_PRIM1	K16593	1.4e-115	387.1	CYP267B1	2.70e-108	323
sp E3VWI3 PNTM_STRAE	K17476	2.9e-259	859.8	CYP161C2	0.0	798
sp E3VWJ9 PENM_STREX	K17476	1.5e-258	857.4	CYP161C3	0.0	809
sp I3DZK9 CYPC_BACMM	K15629	5.4e-190	632.9	CYP152A1	1.15e-162	462
sp O08469 CPXY_BACSU	K16593	5.6e-124	414.7	CYP107J1	0.0	845
sp O31440 CYPC_BACSU	K15629	1.6e-192	641.2	CYP152A1	0.0	870
sp O31785 PKSS_BACSU	K15468	6.3e-269	891.9	CYP107K1	0.0	765
sp O34374 YJIB_BACSU	K23138	3.7e-185	616.0	CYP109B1	0.0	821
sp O34926 CYPX_BACSU	K17474	2.8e-221	734.9	CYP134A1	0.0	840
sp O87605 PIKC_STRVZ	K16006	1.5e-295	979.9	CYP107L1	0.0	829
sp P00183 CPXA_PSEPU	K21569	9.9e-216	716.3	CYP101A1	0.0	863
sp POA513 CP51_MYCBO	K05917	3.1e-176	588.1	CYP51B1	0.0	930
sp POA515 CP121_MYCBO	K17483	6.7e-191	634.7	CYP121A1	0.0	800
sp PODPQ7 GCOA_AMYS7	K23526	6.9e-245	812.7	CYP255A2	0.0	552
sp P14762 CPXI_PRIM2	K21113	6.8e-213	707.5	CYP106A1	0.0	853

sp P18326 CPXE_STRGO	K21146	1.7e-248	824.8	CYP105A1	0.0	824
sp P18327 CPXF_STRGO	K17876	6.6e-142	473.5	CYP105B1	0.0	803
sp P23296 CPXG_STRSQ	K17876	3.9e-113	378.7	CYP105C1	0.0	756
sp P24466 CPXC_RHIRD	K21033	4.5e-175	582.8	CYP103A1	0.0	863
sp P24467 CPXD_RHIRD	K21034	1.3e-214	712.8	CYP104A1	0.0	840
sp P27632 CPXM_BACSH	K23138	5.6e-167	556.2	CYP109A1	0.0	837
sp P29980 CPXN_NOSS1	K23139	1.1e-191	637.7	CYP110A1	0.0	947
sp P33006 CPXL_PSESP	K24391	7.5e-230	763.6	CYP108A1	0.0	894
sp P33271 CPXK_SACEN	K21115	2.9e-287	952.3	CYP107B1	0.0	811
sp P43492 THCB_RHOER	K16046	7.5e-69	232.7	CYP116A1	0.0	908
sp P46373 FAS1_RHOFA	K21035	8.4e-283	937.5	CYP 1050,00	0.0	796
sp P48635 ERYK_SACEN	K14370	2,00E-213	709.1	CYP113A1	0.0	793
sp P53554 BIOI_BACSU	K16593	1.8e-210	699.5	CYP107H1	0.0	825
sp P55540 CPXU_SINFN	K21118	9.7e-270	895.2	CYP117A2	0.0	893
sp P55543 CPXR_SINFN	K21117	1.8e-257	854.2	CYP114A2	0.0	937
sp P55544 CPXP_SINFN	K21116	7.2e-268	888.3	CYP112A2	0.0	808
sp P59954 CP132_MYCBO	K21164	1,00E-100	338.4	CYP132A1	0.0	940
sp P63708 CP123_MYCBO	K23138	2.1e-99	333.7	CYP123A1	0.0	814
sp P63710 CP125_MYCBO	K15981	2.9e-217	721.6	CYP125A1	0.0	901
sp P63712 CP126_MYCBO	K15981	3.2e-112	375.7	CYP126A1	0.0	836
sp P63714 CP128_MYCBO	K21199	1,00E-223	743.5	CYP128A1	0.0	988
sp P63716 C135B_MYCBO	K24241	1.6e-199	663.4	CYP135B1	0.0	939
sp P63718 CP138_MYCBO	K24192	2.1e-235	781.7	CYP138A1	0.0	892
sp P63720 CP139_MYCBO	K23139	2.8e-77	260.6	CYP139A1	0.0	867
sp P63722 CP140_MYCBO	K20789	1.5e-189	631.0	CYP140A1	0.0	878
sp P9WPL0 CP144_MYCTO	K21200	2.2e-204	679.5	CYP144A1	0.0	882
sp P9WPL1 CP144_MYCTU	K21200	2.2e-204	679.5	CYP144A1	0.0	882

sp P9WPL4 CP142_MYCTO	K16046	1.2e-208	693.0	CYP142A1	0.0	757
sp P9WPL5 CP142_MYCTU	K16046	6.3e-220	730.2	CYP142A1	0.0	811
sp P9WPL6 CP141_MYCTO	K13074	6.7e-81	272.7	CYP141A1	0.0	814
sp P9WPL7 CP141_MYCTU	K13074	6.8e-81	272.7	CYP141A1	0.0	816
sp P9WPL8 CP140_MYCTO	K20789	1.5e-189	631.0	CYP140A1	0.0	878
sp P9WPL9 CP140_MYCTU	K20789	1.5e-189	631.0	CYP140A1	0.0	878
sp P9WPM0 CP139_MYCTO	K23139	2.8e-77	260.6	CYP139A1	0.0	867
sp P9WPM1 CP139_MYCTU	K23139	2.8e-77	260.6	CYP139A1	0.0	867
sp P9WPM2 CP138_MYCTO	K24192	2.1e-235	781.7	CYP138A1	0.0	892
sp P9WPM3 CP138_MYCTU	K24192	2.1e-235	781.7	CYP138A1	0.0	892
sp P9WPM4 CP137_MYCTO	K24241	2,00E-129	432.4	CYP137A1	0.0	938
sp P9WPM5 CP137_MYCTU	K24241	2,00E-129	432.4	CYP137A1	0.0	938
sp P9WPM6 CP136_MYCTO	K24392	9.4e-86	288.7	CYP136A1	0.0	1021
sp P9WPM7 CP136_MYCTU	K24392	9.4e-86	288.7	CYP136A1	0.0	1021
sp P9WPM8 C135B_MYCTO	K24241	1.6e-199	663.4	CYP135B1	0.0	939
sp P9WPM9 C135B_MYCTU	K24241	1.6e-199	663.4	CYP135B1	0.0	939
sp P9WPN0 C135A_MYCTO	K24241	1.2e-187	624.2	CYP135A1	0.0	912
sp P9WPN1 C135A_MYCTU	K24241	1.2e-187	624.2	CYP135A1	0.0	912
sp P9WPN2 CP132_MYCTO	K21164	1,00E-100	338.4	CYP132A1	0.0	940
sp P9WPN3 CP132_MYCTU	K21164	4.3e-100	336.4	CYP132A1	0.0	942
sp P9WPN4 CP130_MYCTO	K21119	8.4e-229	760.0	CYP130A1	0.0	829
sp P9WPN5 CP130_MYCTU	K21119	8.4e-229	760.0	CYP130A1	0.0	829
sp P9WPN6 CP128_MYCTO	K21199	1,00E-223	743.5	CYP128A1	0.0	988
sp P9WPN7 CP128_MYCTU	K21199	1,00E-223	743.5	CYP128A1	0.0	988
sp P9WPN8 CP126_MYCTO	K15981	3.2e-112	375.7	CYP126A1	0.0	836
sp P9WPN9 CP126_MYCTU	K15981	3.2e-112	375.7	CYP126A1	0.0	836
sp P9WPP0 CP125_MYCTO	K15981	2.9e-217	721.6	CYP125A1	0.0	901

sp P9WPP1 CP125_MYCTU	K15981	2.9e-217	721.6	CYP125A1	0.0	901
sp P9WPP4 CP123_MYCTO	K23138	2.1e-99	333.7	CYP123A1	0.0	814
sp P9WPP5 CP123_MYCTU	K23138	2.1e-99	333.7	CYP123A1	0.0	814
sp P9WPP6 CP121_MYCTO	K17483	6.7e-191	634.7	CYP121A1	0.0	800
sp P9WPP7 CP121_MYCTU	K17483	6.7e-191	634.7	CYP121A1	0.0	800
sp P9WPP8 CP51_MYCTO	K05917	3.1e-176	588.1	CYP51B1	0.0	930
sp P9WPP9 CP51_MYCTU	K05917	3.1e-176	588.1	CYP51B1	0.0	930
sp Q00441 CPXJ_SACEN	K14366	2.6e-248	824.0	CYP107A1	0.0	804
sp Q06069 CPXM_PRIMG	K21114	1,00E-281	934.1	CYP106A2	0.0	846
sp Q0S7M1 CP125_RHOJR	K15981	1.4e-220	732.5	CYP125A14P	0.0	975
sp Q53215 Y4VG_SINFN	K21569	9.3e-90	301.4	CYP127A1	0.0	846
sp Q54823 DNRQ_STRPE	K15952	7.4e-304	1007.5	CYP131A1	0.0	845
sp Q59203 CPXP_BRADU	K21116	1,00E-266	884.5	CYP112A1	0.0	803
sp Q59204 CPXR_BRADU	K21117	2.3e-257	853.8	CYP114A3v1	0.0	793
sp Q59205 CPXU_BRADU	K21118	2,00E-264	877.6	CYP117A3	0.0	816
sp Q59723 CPXO_PSEPU	K05525	1,00E-223	742.8	CYP111A1	0.0	835
sp Q59831 CPS2_STRCC	K21146	4,00E-239	793.9	CYP105A3	0.0	828
sp Q59971 DOXA_STRS5	K15955	1.4e-295	980.1	CYP129A1	0.0	840
sp Q59990 CP120_SYNY3	K24392	1.4e-196	654.0	CYP120A1	0.0	902
sp Q5IZM4 CP51_MYCVP	K05917	6.5e-179	597.0	CYP51B1	0.0	939
sp Q5J1R4 NOCL_NOCUT	K19106	3.2e-262	869.6	CYP107AC1	1.69e-144	415
sp Q6N8N2 CYPA2_RHOPA	K22553	1.4e-192	640.4	CYP199A2	0.0	838
sp Q825I8 CYP28_STRAW	K17876	8.1e-212	703.7	CYP105D7	0.0	804
sp Q82IY3 PTLI_STRAW	K15907	5.7e-247	820.1	CYP183A1	0.0	911
sp Q83WF5 MYCCI_MICGR	K24292	5.5e-233	772.8	CYP105L2	0.0	768
sp Q84HB6 NCSB3_STRCZ	K20420	2,00E-167	559.7	CYP154J1	0.0	837
sp Q87AV9 C1332_XYLFT	K16593	4.1e-93	313.0	CYP133B2v2	0.0	803

sp Q87AX5 C1331_XYLFT	K16593	2,00E-101	340.4	CYP133B1v2	0.0	830
sp Q8RN03 C5C4_AMYOR	K16447	3.1e-258	856.6	CYP165C4	0.0	827
sp Q8RN04 C5B3_AMYOR	K16446	1.4e-258	857.9	CYP165B3	0.0	806
sp Q8RN05 C5A3_AMYOR	K16445	2.3e-249	827.4	CYP165A3	0.0	794
sp Q8VQF6 CINA_CITBR	K21120	1.3e-288	956.5	CYP176A1	0.0	830
sp Q93MI2 DOXA_STRCO	K15955	1,00E-277	921.2	CYP129A2	0.0	756
sp Q9FCA6 C1582_STRCO	K13074	3.3e-212	705.2	CYP158A2	0.0	719
sp Q9KIZ4 C167_SORCE	K16400	1.3e-260	864.7	CYP167A1	0.0	840
sp Q9KZF5 C1581_STRCO	K19628	1.7e-250	831.0	CYP158A1	0.0	811
sp Q9L4U5 AKNT_STRGJ	K15947	0	1020.6	CYP131A1	3.61e-79	251
sp Q9L9F9 NOVI_STRNV	K12702	2.1e-281	932.8	CYP163A1	0.0	839
sp Q9PGC5 C1331_XYLFA	K16593	5.4e-101	339.0	CYP133B1v1	0.0	832
sp Q9PGE6 C1332_XYLFA	K16593	8.3e-95	318.6	CYP133B2v2	0.0	803
sp Q9ZAU3 DOXA_STRPE	K15955	3.7e-294	975.4	CYP129A2	0.0	828
sp Q9ZGH8 DES8_STRVZ	K16005	6.7e-277	918.6	CYP131A1	3.21e-64	210
sp Q9ZHQ1 TYLH1_STRFR	K15991	1.1e-230	765.7	CYP105L1	0.0	830

